

D5.1: Sustainability assessment of state-of-the- art lithium-ion cell production

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1.1. SUMMARY SHEET

<i>Project Acronym</i>	BATMACHINE
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1.3. DOCUMENT CHANGE LOG

Version number	Date	Organization name	Description
0.1	05/06/2024	VUB	First draft
0.7	30/06/2024	VUB	Economical & environmental review
0.8	07/08/2024	VUB	Final draft
0.9	14/08/2024	FOM and NFT	Deliverable review
1.0	28/08/2024	VUB	Revised draft
1.1	30/08/2024	VUB	Final version
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1.4. List of Participants

N.	Logo	Name	Short Name	Country
1		VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	VUB	Belgium
2		FUNDACION TEKNIKER	TEKNIKER	Spain
3		SKZ-KFE GGMBH	SKZ	Germany
4		FOM TECHNOLOGIES A/S	FOM	Denmark
5		DEEP BLUE SRL	DBL	Italy
6		NETZSCH FEINMAHLTECHNIK GMBH	NFT	Germany
7		RHEINISCH-WESTFAELISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE AACHEN	RWTH AACHEN	Germany
8		SINTEF AS	SINTEF	Norway
8a		SINTEF OCEAN AS	SINTEF-OCEAN	Norway
9		POMEGA ENERJI DEPOLAMA TEKNOLOJILERI ANONIM SIRKETI	POMEGA	Turkey
10		CEGASA ENERGIA S.L.U.	CEGASA	Spain
11		LECLANCHÉ GMBH	LEC	Germany

1.5. ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	Extended
AAM	Anode Active Material
BEV	Battery electric vehicle
BoM	Bill of materials
CAM	Cathode Active Material
CBAM	Carbon border adjustment mechanism
CIRAF	Cobalt Industry Responsible Assessment Framework
CO2-eq	CO2 equivalent
CRM	Critical raw material
CSS	Country-specific sectors
E-LCA	Environmental Life cycle assessment
GHG	Greenhouse gas
Gr	Graphite
GTAP	Global Trade Analysis Project
GWP	Global warming potential
IA	Impact assessment
IC	Impact category
ICEV	Internal combustion engine vehicle
ILO	International Labour Organization
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KPI	Key performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life cycle cost
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LFP	Lithium Iron Phosphate
LIB	Lithium-ion Battery
LMO	Lithium Manganese Oxide
LP	Linear programming
Mrheq	Medium risk hours equivalent
NCA	Nickel Cobalt Aluminum
NMC	Nickel Manganese Cobalt
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PBCM	Process-based cost modelling
PEF	Product Environmental footprint
PSIA	Product Social Impact Assessment
PSILCA	Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment database
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SETAC	Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
SHDB	Social Hotspots Database
SHI	Social Hotspot Index
Si	Silicone
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TCO	Total cost of ownership
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
xEV	Electric vehicle

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1.8. Executive summary

This report aims to establish a benchmark regarding environmental, economic, and social dimensions of cell manufacturing. It starts with a literature review on cell manufacturing and ends with a multi-dimensional assessment of Pomega LFP-Gr 100Ah (environmental and economic) and GIGAGERMA NMC622-Gr DE-89 (environmental, economic, and social) cell manufacturing.

GIGAGERMA is the name given to a made-up German cell manufacturing line. This manufacturing line was designed to represent a 0.250 GWh production capacity.

These detailed assessments at the manufacturing process level will help BATMACHINE's KPIs be measured and eventually reached.

The environmental and economic life cycle assessment confirmed the lion's share of the raw material under a cradle-to-gate (i.e. From the mining to the door of the factory) perspective.

The direct impact of cell manufacturing energy consumption is minor, often accounting for a small share of the overall impact in the 16 categories assessed. However, improvements can still be made on both energy efficiency and material used. For example, a solvent switch from NMP to water, dry coating or drying energy source switch can help achieve IC reductions. Moreover, if specific energy density increases, *ceteris paribus*, the overall assessment will be improved.

The narrow margin left is hence, according to the data we could obtain, mostly dependent on the energy consumption or technical specificity of the cell or material used in the process such as solvent or binder. Targets were set, energy efficiency due to increase by 20%, cost to be reduced by 5%, GHG intensity by 15% and 50% of the environmental IC should be reduced according to KPIs 3.2, 3.3, 4.1 and 4.2 respectively.

When looking at the POMEGA manufacturing line result, the production cost is estimated to be $[80.64, 100.20] \text{€ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ and GHG intensity of $93.5 \text{ kgCO}_2\text{eq kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$. This would translate in the necessity of a production cost reduction ranging in $[4.032, 5.01] \text{€ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ and a GHG intensity reduction of $14.025 \text{ kgCO}_2\text{eq kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ to reach the target fixed. The economic target could be reached by waste avoidance, or simply a combination of energy and material cost. For the GWP of cell manufacturing, the change in energy mix as planned by Pomega should already benefit from most of the expected GHG reduction. For the other environmental IC, NMP recovery or waste avoidance could achieve this.

The GIGAGERMA manufacturing line results in a production cost of $[116.95, 173] \text{€ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ and $99 \text{ kgCO}_2\text{eq kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$. This would translate in the necessity of a production cost reduction ranging in $[5.85, 8.65] \text{€ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ and a GHG intensity reduction of $14.85 \text{ kgCO}_2\text{eq kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ in order to reach the target fixed. The GHG target cannot be achieved solely by using a different energy mix, as it is responsible for around $10 \text{ kgCO}_2\text{eq kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$, improvements of different types shall be investigated such as the one proposed within BATMACHINE. Other actions can probably lead to the achievement of these goals; however, we could not quantify them in this report.

This study allowed us to highlight some crucial conclusions for battery manufacturing:

- The final production cost of an average cell is majorly determined by the chemistry and hence the raw material embedded within the final product.
- The cost share not allocated to raw material but to the manufacturing itself is also dependent on the chemistry and is associated with the energy consumption from condition control, drying or ageing.

- Scrap within the manufacturer's production line can have a high cost, as for each of the many processes some scrap originating from imperfect dimensioning or destructive testing can occur.

According to grey literature (e.g. BNEF reports), most of the savings done on battery cell manufacturing occurred thanks to the many improvements within the manufacturer line leading to direct energy-saving and relative energy consumption degrowth associated to the energy density increase. The high decrease in production cost observed in the last decade is then mostly achieved by techniques which include :

- Energy saving thanks to an optimised design of the manufacturing line
- Scrap avoidance with more accurate machinery and non-destructive testing
- New technology used within the manufacturing line

Despite this conclusion, performance at the economic & environmental level can still be improved but they will provide more & more limited benefits.

Main conclusions from the results from S-LCA

Concerning the social aspects, a S-LCA was conducted based on the Social Hotspots Database (SHDB) to analyse the social sustainability of the DE-89 Energy Cell produced by GIGAGERMA. The supply chain composition was defined by describing how the production costs were distributed among the manufacturing steps to each sector/country pair, considering two case studies defined by the origin of exogenous materials: CASE 1-China and CASE 2-Japan.

The impact assessment showed that Health & Safety and Governance were the social categories most affected in both case studies, but social impacts of CASE 1-China were more than twice of CASE 2-Japan. Some subcategories in Labor Rights & Decent Work category were significantly impacted as well. The three greatest impacts both for CASE 1-China and CASE 2-Japan were found at the same subcategories: Occupational Toxics & Hazards, Injuries and Fatalities, and Forced Labor. Regarding the manufacturing process of the cells, the most important contributions to social hotspots for CASE 1-China were found in the CAM manufacturing, whilst in CASE 2-Japan, the Separator operational input posed the main impact. The sensitivity analysis conducted to estimate the influence of the CAM input coming from China showed that the social impacts could be reduced considering Germany as an alternative origin, but Japan would perform the best on social sustainability optimization. Although the literature addressing S-LCA on NMC622-Gr batteries comprehensively is scarce, based on the social hotspots reported in the present study, similar recommendations can be proposed to optimise the social sustainability of the state-of-the-art LIB cell production line. The CAM operational input poses the greatest risks when comparing product systems in different potential locations, especially for workers and supply chains located in China.

1.9. Partners' Contributions

Partner institution	Sections	Description of the contribution
VUB	Environmental & cost life cycle assessment and the rest	Organisation; merging and economic/environmental LCA.
TEKNIKER	Social life cycle assessment	All chapters about social assessment
POMEGA	POMEGA background data	Provided all the LCI; average data quality

2. Project Overview

The BATMACHINE project is centred on strengthening Europe's battery cell industrial manufacturing value chain by developing new battery cell manufacturing machinery. This will be done while giving priority to minimising the energy for cell production, enhancing plant efficiency rates, and integrating intelligent control processes to reduce scrap.

The project will develop and implement an optimised and energy-efficient process chain considering:

- Slurry mixing (automated modular process set-up including monitoring techniques).
- Exclusive slot-die coating and drying novel machinery (with one side coating, a coating speed of 1m/min up to 20m/min and a web width of 300 mm).
- A calendaring tool to be integrated into a battery manufacturer for process optimisation.

Moreover, intelligent control processes and Industry 4.0 will be intensively integrated through the creation of collaborative and FAIR data space for battery production. Digital interfaces between battery manufacturing equipment, control systems, and engineers will be developed to build universal digitalisation tools to enhance battery production and create a battery passport. The environmental and economic impact of different machinery, production line configurations, and factory designs will be studied in depth to reduce the cost and energy consumption of manufacturing processes.

To reach two of the project objectives, KPIs have been defined within the grant agreement and six of them are directly engaged within this deliverable:

- BATMACHINE Objective 3: Cost and energy optimisation of the battery manufacturing process, including integrating low-carbon and low-emission energy sources.
 - KPI 3.2: The energy efficiency of the whole battery production process for cell production, should be increased by at least 20%
 - KPI 3.3: The production costs of the whole battery production process for cell production, should be decreased by at least 5%
 - KPI 3.4: The integration of renewable energies to supply the manufacturing of batteries will be assessed. This integration should lead to a decrease of energy costs and emissions. Compared to the average EU grid carbon mix, a minimum reduction of 15 % of greenhouse gas emission is targeted BATMACHINE
- Objective 4: Implement ecological standards in the design phase and investigate the environmental and social impacts of different machinery and supply chains to come to best practice proposals
 - KPI 4.1: Sustainable by design: the implementation of eco-design measures, including early-phase LCA, and S-LCA, should lead to a decrease in greenhouse gas emissions of at least 15%.
 - KPI 4.2: Quantify 16 different environmental impact categories of which 50% will decrease.
 - KPI 4.3: Social benefits for the whole society in terms of impact in economic wealth, as well as on the creation of new jobs.

3. Introduction

The deliverable (D5.1) of task 5.1 of the work package “Energy, cost & sustainability assessment” consists in establishing a benchmark of battery-cell manufacturing to assess the sustainability of the lithium-ion battery (LIB) cell production line. Beyond the environmental and economic concerns, sustainability is also related to social aspects. This benchmark comprises the socio-economic & environmental dimensions. Life Cycle Costing (LCC), Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) and Life Cycle Assessment are applied to data collected from project partners.

Particular attention shall be given to the steps of slurry mixing, slot die coating & drying and calendaring (e.g. for both electrodes) steps as these three processes are developed in BATMACHINE and to the KPIs of the project (e.g. 20% improvements in energy efficiency for the whole battery manufacturing, an increase of production cost reduction of 5%, 15% GWP reductions, 50% of 16 IC are to diminish, social benefits to be improved).

This report provides the identified state of the art of battery manufacturing life cycle assessment (LCA) from academic literature, moreover an LCA of cells manufactured by project partner, DE-89 and LFP-100 for GIGAGERMA and Pomega respectively, for their manufacturing line is done. GIGAGERMA is the name given to a made-up German cell manufacturing line, this manufacturing line was designed to represent a 0.250 GWh production capacity. The collected data will be used to benchmark the partner's manufacturing line's current performance, and at a later time assess the evolution proposed within the frame of BATMACHINE. The S-LCA was only conducted on the GIGAGERMA's LIB cell, due to limitations on data availability in the project at the time of conducting the inventory analysis. We aim to revise the goal and scope of the reference system in task 5.5 and D5.5., to be aligned with the LCA and LCC analysis (e.g. including POMEGA's LFP).

4. Methodology

Each dimension of the LCA here is done following different standards:

Figure 1 Guidelines used for life cycle assessment

4.1. Life cycle assessment of production lines

The four main steps of an LCA (ISO, 2006a, 2006b) are presented in Figure 2 Steps of a life cycle assessment and include all the life cycle stages of the product for a gate-to-gate perspective, from the active material to the cell.

Raw material extraction and recycling will be considered within some benchmark examples but are not a particular focus since the target of the BATMACHINE project is to assess the benefits and identify the improvement potential of battery manufacturing.

To identify the processes and parameters influencing environmental performances of the production line of Li-ion batteries throughout a cradle-to-gate life cycle, a Life Cycle

Figure 2 Steps of a life cycle assessment

Assessment (LCA) is performed, based on the European guideline for product environmental footprint (PEF) more precisely (Andreasi Bassi, S. *et al.*, 2023). To assess the social impacts, a social LCA (S-LCA) is performed, following the same four steps and based on the UNEP Guidelines on S-LCA (Benoit Norris *et al.*, 2020).

- **Goal definition** addresses what is to be assessed and why the assessment is performed. S-LCA goal is to assess impacts on well-being, and in principle, any affected human is considered a stakeholder. Prevailing stakeholder groups are the

workers across the life cycle, the local or regional communities affected, and the product users. Additionally, S-LCA may consider other stakeholders who can affect or can be affected by decisions taken in the product life cycle, e.g., shareholders, company owners and other decision-makers.

- **Scope definition** addresses the choices made to perform the assessment and its limitations. In this phase the system boundaries are established, defining which parts of the life cycle and which processes are required for providing the function defined by the functional unit. In terms of impact allocation, several processes need to be considered throughout the product life cycle to provide the functional unit. One of the frequent approaches used in the literature is to allocate social impacts of the company to the process, based on the working time required to perform it.
- **Inventory analysis** has the purpose of collecting the data outlined through the goal and scope definition. In LCA, the data aim to capture environmental exchanges, where physical flows such as mass and energy to and from the processes are included in the assessment. For assessing social impacts, this approach cannot be applied. Instead, some interplay between the process and its social surroundings must be specified to collect data. Different approaches exist to mitigate the data collection challenge, but the most feasible is to use databases of social impacts related to sectors and countries.
- **Impact assessment** uses models to translate inventory data into impacts. It consists of the elements: classification, characterisation, normalisation and weighting. Social LCA is conducted similarly to environmental LCA, with the same iterative approach and many feedback loops between the different phases, and the initial steps for the analysis design and configuration are the same. Nevertheless, the approach for impact assessment is different, and it consists of the aggregation of all social impacts weighted by the national and sectoral risk factors. In the databases available for modelling social LCA (SHDB and PSILCA), impacts are provided in comparable medium-risk hours.
- **Interpretation** analyses the outcome of the previous phases following the goal of the study and tries to answer the question posed in the goal definition.

4.2. System Boundaries

The system boundaries are taken from (Andreasi Bassi, S. *et al.*, 2023), which compartmentalises different steps of the life cycle of an EV battery. The system boundary used in this study goes up to cell production and does not include the Cooling system assembly, but includes from the top of the manufacturing process, Active material production (Cathode and anode) to Cell production.

Source: JRC

Figure 3 The system boundaries identified by JRC.

4.3. Scope

Within the (Andreas Bassi, S. *et al.*, 2023) the functional unit adopted is the total amount of kWh provided over the entire lifetime of the battery.

However, due to the scope of BATMACHINE, the production line of LIB cell the functional unit adopted here is the production of one kWh of storage capacity as often done in literature (Jinasena, Burheim and Strømman, 2021; Degen and Krätzig, 2023; Erakca *et al.*, 2023; Kallitsis *et al.*, 2023).

Moreover, when assessing the production line of LIB it is important to take into consideration the production capacity (e.g. GWh/year) and how the data has been transformed to fit a yearly production.

4.3.1. Objectives in relation with the project

A list of predefined KPIs used as metric to reach the projects objective have been defined, 5 of them can be considered in this report :

- KPI 3.2: The energy efficiency of the whole battery production process for cell production, should be increased by at least 20%.
- KPI 3.3: The production costs of the whole battery production process for cell production, should be decreased by at least 5%
- KPI 4.1: Sustainable by design: the implementation of eco-design measures, including early-phase LCA, and S-LCA, should lead to a decrease in greenhouse gas emissions of at least 15%.
- KPI 4.2: Quantify 16 different environmental impact categories of which 50% will decrease.
- KPI 4.3: Social benefits for the whole society in terms of impact in economic wealth, as well as on the creation of new jobs.

KPIs 3.2, 4.1 and 4.2 can be associated to environmental life cycle assessment, while KPI 3.2 and 3.3 to the economic life cycle assessment.

The KPI 4.3 and 4.1 are also part of the social life cycle assessment done by Tekniker.

These KPI should help us to conclude the literature review, sustainability assessment of the production line of the different manufacturing partners and will be assessed with respect to the function unit defined above, (i.e. per kWh of energy storage capacity).

These objectives should be considered under the prism of the project, battery production machinery but also over the limited yet existing responsibility of the manufacturer hence they should be reach by less energy consumption within the manufacturing process, change of solvent or other exogenous material however a tabula rasa scenario such as a change of chemistry will not be considered.

4.4. Economical Life Cycle Assessment

Each economic assessment made use of the data present in the annexes or hidden due to confidentiality, if they are disclosed then you will find them under the names “Pomega data” and “GIGAGERMA data”.

4.4.1. Methodology

The economic assessment was done with a VUB model based on linear programming, developed in a PhD student's work (Ferrari *et al.*, 2024). It allows easily represent a production process and to eventually schedule it to minimize a criterion under certain constraints.

The model can provide a detailed assessment of a manufacturing line, however, it is highly dependent on data. Hence only a limited assessment could be done due to the limitation of the data collected about the manufacturing line of Pomega and GIGAGERMA. This model belongs to the bottom-up process modelling general type of economic model.

In this case, it is simply used to represent the manufacturing flow and account for cost.

The values are estimation and do not claim to represent the real production cost of both Pomega and GIGAGERMA.

4.4.2. Cost compartment

The cost compartments generally used in cell manufacturing are the following :

- Depreciation building
- Maintenance
- Energy
- Overhead
- Scrap
- Labor
- Depreciation machine
- Material

They might differ in name or in what they quantitatively include but their meaning remains the same. The cost compartments directly computed are different depending on the manufacturing partner as it is dependent on the data collected from each manufacturing line.

In the case of Pomega, enough data was collected and shared to provide estimation for Materials cost, Labor cost and Energy cost. In the case of GIGAGERMA enough data was collected and shared to provide estimation for Materials cost and Energy cost.

Due to the lack of information, some cost compartments have not been modelled or quantified directly such as:

- Scrap
- Building & land
- Machinery
- Maintenance
- Overhead

However, all of these compartments are available in the final results thanks to two studies which allow us to extrapolate both the final cost in € kWh_{cell}^{-1} and a possible cost share for each compartment.

4.5. Environmental Life Cycle Assessment

As for the economic assessment the environmental one made use of the data present in the annexes or hidden due to confidentiality, if they are disclosed then you will find them under the names “Pomega data” and “GIGAGERMA data”.

4.5.1. Implementation

Within Brightway (Mutel, 2017), or more precisely through Activity-Browser everything was implemented as provided by Pomega or GIGAGERMA hence no modification of the source data except for the change of unit (i.e. for Pomega the separator and the housing were converted from m² to kg and piece to kg) but the output is expressed in kWh_{cell}^{-1} instead of a cell (GIGAGERMA) or batch of cells (Pomega).

In the case of Pomega, this leads to a quantity of reference product equal to 244 as every step produces enough for 244 kWh of cell capacity.

In the case of GIGAGERMA, this leads to a quantity equal to 0.242 as every step produces enough for 0.24 kWh of cell capacity (i.e. The DE-89 cell capacity) or a little bit more (0.3872) for the electrode preparation part due to different granularity of the electrode production process.

This was done not to hide the original information and allow reproducibility. Moreover, this allows a future user to estimate non-linear relationships depending on the production output.

4.5.2. Background database

The EcolInvent 3.9.1 database (Wernet *et al.*, 2016) was used as a background database, all other sources originate either from research projects or literature.

4.5.3. Impact categories & methodology

The methodology EF 3.1(Joint Research Centre (European Commission) *et al.*, 2023) as advised by the European Commission (*Commission Recommendation (EU) 2021/2279 of 15 December 2021 on the use of the Environmental Footprint methods to measure and communicate the life cycle environmental performance of products and organisations*, 2021) from the Joint Research Center was used, 16 impacts were computed as more than 50% of them must diminish according to KPI 4.2 :

- climate change
- acidification
- ecotoxicity: freshwater
- energy resources: non-renewable
- eutrophication: freshwater
- eutrophication: marine
- eutrophication: terrestrial
- human toxicity: carcinogenic
- human toxicity: non-carcinogenic

- ionising radiation: human health
- land use
- material resources: metals/minerals
- ozone depletion
- particulate matter formation
- photochemical oxidant formation: human health
- water use

Moreover, a focus on the impact category (IC) climate change will also be done as KPI 4.1 fix a target of 15% GHG reduction while KPI 4.2 expect at least 50% of 16 IC to decrease.

4.6. Social Life Cycle Assessment

As for the environmental and economic assessment, the social one made use of the data present in the annexes or hidden due to confidentiality. If disclosed, then they are found under the names “Pomega data” and “GIGAGERMA data”.

The S-LCA presented in this deliverable was based on the methodological phases explained above, and the **Social Hotspots Database (SHDB) was used in SimaPro** to analyse the social sustainability of the existing cell manufacturing lines set as benchmark in BATMACHINE. Figure 4 shows a schematic diagram of the S-LCA methodology and the basic elements of each phase.

Figure 4 Methodological phases of a social LCA followed in the present study, based on the SHDB database and model.

5. Assessment of Lithium-ion cell manufacturing

5.1. Introduction

This chapter will analyse the recent socio-economic and environmental results of cell manufacturing with a predisposition for work embedding manufacturing process step details for the NMC622-Gr and LFP-Gr cells.

First, a review of previous work is done, focusing on the socio-economic and environmental dimensions of cell manufacturing. Moreover, an energy consumption emphasis of the manufacturing process will be perceived as it is a value peculiar to every manufacturing process whereas the BoM can show less diversity.

Consideration for raw materials is again only superfluous and lightly covered as these are not easy changes to be done on a cell manufacturing line when considering chemistry change.

The cell manufacturing assessments are of three types:

- Bottom-up (which considers the manufacturing process in detail with the help of a model or an LCI or both) such as Process-Based-Modelling
- Meta approaches (by extrapolating tendencies such as learning rate, scaling effect etc)
- Expert survey (consultation of experts from the field to evaluate the cost)

All of them can give results of the final production cost of the cell, however, due to the scope of the project the approach we will focus on the bottom-up, or PBCM one, as we can then base it on the LCI collected with the manufacturing partners.

A data collection will take place, however, production cost or GHG, comparability is not ensured for the reasons explained below, hence the choice is to rather indicate documents providing information/or methodology rather than comparing the value itself.

Costs are nearly always specified differently due to:

- the year of accounting,
- the economic cost compartment division or consideration (e.g. margin, insurance, labour, utilities, R&D, land, machinery, opex)
- the technical cost compartment (e.g. material, cost per step, cost per room, cost per tuple (room, step), manufacturing processed is different)

Moreover, even if the cost is divided in the same compartment other issues arise:

- Product is technically (i.e. physically) different (e.g. chemistry, format)
- Material costs are different
- Location leads to different utilities cost
- Processes are different.
- Performance of the service is different

5.2. Model or publications with a process-level analysis of cell production

Data was collected from literature, grey literature and VUB inside sources, more than 220 papers were analysed and more than 50 were used only for the cost assessment review.

All of this led to the collection of sources within Table 1 providing analysis for cell manufacturing, from detailed process-based analysis to a literature review passed by more economic models:

- Socio/Economic factor
- Material costs
- Manufacturing cost per process
- Location
- Scrap

The data obtained originate from inventory and simulations, the inventory can come from primary, secondary or tertiary sources. The methods used by the simulations range from an Excel model compiling data from diverse sources (Knehr *et al.*, 2022) to complex models taking into account temperature, humidity, size of each room of the factory, flux and stocks of intermediate product between manufacturing steps and employee working hours

(Schönemann *et al.*, 2016; Weeber *et al.*, 2020) or deep technical integration (Schönemann *et al.*, 2019).

Publication	Focus			Model			Cost compartment					Consideration					
	Energy	Cost	Environment	Analysis	Process based	LCI	Economical	Material	Energy	Process level	Room	Economical	Scale	Chemistry	Cell format	Location	Scrap
(Wentker, Greenwood and Leker, 2019)		X						X					X	X			
(Jinasena, Burheim and Strømman, 2021)	X				X				X		X		X	X	X		X
(Orangi and Strømman, 2022)		X			X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
(Turcheniuk <i>et al.</i> , 2021)		X		X			X	X									
(Duffner, Krätzig and Leker, 2020)				X	X			X	X	X		X		X	X	X	X
(Duffner <i>et al.</i> , 2020)		X			X			X	X	X		X		X	X	X	X
(Berckmans <i>et al.</i> , 2017)		X				X	X	X	X			X		X			
(Gutsch and Leker, 2024)					X			X	X	X		X		X	X	X	X
(Mauler, Duffner and Leker, 2021)					X			X	X	X		X		X	X	X	X
(von Drachenfels <i>et al.</i> , 2022)			X	X		X		X	X	X	X			X	X		
(Sun <i>et al.</i> , 2020)			X	X		X			X	X							
(Degen and Schütte, 2022)			X						X	X	X	X	X			X	
(Weeber <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	X				X				X	X	X					X	
(Degen and Krätzig, 2023)		X			X		X		X	X	X						
(Schönemann <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	X				X				X	X							
(Kallitsis, 2022)	X			X					X								
(Schmuck <i>et al.</i> , 2018)		X		X													
(Duffner <i>et al.</i> , 2021)																	
(Nykvist and Nilsson, 2015)		X		X													
(Bielewski <i>et al.</i> , 2023)		X		X			X	X									
(Thomitzek <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	X				X												
(Wessel <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	X				X				X	X	X						X
(Knehr <i>et al.</i> , 2022)		X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
(Sakti <i>et al.</i> , 2017)		X		X													
(Mauler <i>et al.</i> , 2021)		X		X													
(Hewawasam <i>et al.</i> , 2022)		X			X		X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
(Nelson <i>et al.</i> , 2019)		X			X												
(Schütte, Degen and Walter, 2024)	X				X					X							
(Orangi <i>et al.</i> , 2023)		X			X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
(Orangi <i>et al.</i> , 2024)		X			X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
(Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	X	X		X	X					X			X				

Table 1 Main analysis at the process level for the gate-to-gate cell manufacturing.

5.3.Review for cell manufacturing cost assessment

Some studies or reviews also used statistical analysis (Nykvist and Nilsson, 2015; Schmidt *et al.*, 2017) but with a more macro-economic approach, trying to identify the learning rate of the battery manufacturing sector and provide an estimate of future battery pack cost per kWh_{cell}^{-1} .

Figure 5 Cost of Li-ion battery packs in BEV. Data are from multiple types of sources and trace both reported costs for the industry and costs for market-leading manufacturers. (Nykvist and Nilsson, 2015)

Even with scarce data (Nykvist and Nilsson, 2015) ended with a learning rate of 9% and 6%, for the overall sector and the market leader respectively (based on 53 unique estimates).

As previously highlighted by (Schünemann, 2015; Dai *et al.*, 2019; Thomitzek *et al.*, 2019), drying of electrodes and dry rooms are the main consumers with a cumulated energy consumption share of more than 60%.

BATPAC model (Nelson *et al.*, 2015, 2019; Knehr *et al.*, 2022) is a recognised model which allows detailed process modelling, with a total cost of ownership (TCO) cost, by considering scale, machinery, materials, cell format and socio-economic data it is a complete tool with transparent and openly accessible data and hypotheses.

In 2015, (Nelson *et al.*, 2015) using BATPAC computed a cost of $\$161 kWh_{pack}^{-1}$ for an NMC441-G battery pack with an energy density of 0.1593 kWh/kg is listed in the range $\$161-189 kWh_{pack}^{-1}$ depending on the metrics (i.e. Usable or total energy).

(Wood, Li and Daniel, 2015) focus on a few process changes that could be done to the battery manufacturing process such as using water instead of NMP as solvent (with better dispersion and lower boiling point this would reduce cost at the different drying and formation times) or increasing the electrode thickness to increase the energy density is also proposed. The maximum computed saving of 26.4% reduced the cost from $\$502.8 kWh_{cell}^{-1}$ to $\$370.3 kWh_{cell}^{-1}$.

The study (Schünemann *et al.*, 2016) using the modified simulation model of (Schünemann, 2015) also highlights the 75% share of raw material within the production cost in a cradle-to-gate approach (which includes energy, capital, depreciation, direct labour and material), in descending order, the precursor and additive/solvent, the separator, the current collectors, the cell frame and the electrolyte. Excluding material costs allows a more pertinent look for a battery manufacturer, 20% for the coating and drying, 25% for the vacuum drying and 14% for the stacking to cite the three highest.

(Sakti *et al.*, 2017) classify the forecasting model into three categories expert elicitation, technical cost modelling (i.e. bottom-up model) and extrapolations (e.g. learning curve/technological learning), they then combine elicited expertise and PBCM (bottom-up modelling) to compare component-based projection with battery pack cost performance and end-up with 50% of the expert being inconsistent with their numbers, this 50% being consultants for the battery industry and the other half being from the battery industry with coherent projection.

(Ciez and Whitacre, 2017) compare cylindrical and prismatic cells to conclude that the production cost per kWh can be lower for prismatic as the mass of inactive material per kWh is lower than for cylindrical. They also provide machinery cost and cost of storage based on BATPAC. The material take 40% of the raw material cost, the final optimistic costs are equal to \$180 kWh_{cell}^{-1} for NMC441 and \$206 kWh_{cell}^{-1} for Nickel Cobalt Aluminium (NCA).

Yet another cost-focus study (Berckmans *et al.*, 2017) predicts a cost of 670 $\$/kWh_{cell}^{-1}$ for a Nickel-Cobalt-Manganese (NMC622-GrSi) from a PBCM model that accounts for margin and even middleman reseller share where already 28% originate from the cathode. For the prediction a combination of PBCM and learning curve for each component (e.g. material, labour, overhead, profit) based on expected future sales detailed within their study, surprisingly this study is quite close to the current price :

PREDICTION OF SALES PRICE BATTERY I

Figure 6 Prediction of the sales price of battery I up to 2030. (Berckmans *et al.*, 2017)

In 2018, (Schmuck *et al.*, 2018) concluded their review by saying that the cost reduction drivers are economies of scale and automation, they also said that no chemistry will

dominate and that next-generation technology such as Li-metal-based or beyond Lithium (e.g. Na or Mg) chemistry will not soon replace the current generation due to the already large investment and maturity of the sector and difficult entry for non-cost competitive technology. As of today, we see Na chemistry being developed, for a different market, and LiFePO₄(LFP) also spreading.

(Kwade *et al.*, 2018) analyse the battery cost, the material content of battery and propose some new machinery techniques that could be to reduce production cost of cells. They also highlight the fact that many distinct manufacturing processes co-exist due to different cell formats, chemistry, and manufacturing technologies, some of which reach up to 25 steps. Even with an excellent 99.5% success rate at each step, the final success rate will be 88.2%. They analyse the accumulated value after each step of a battery manufacturing step using

BatPac:

Figure 7 Breakdown of manufacturing cost at cell level (Kwade *et al.*, 2018)

Another cost study focusing on materials used within battery manufacturing state that 60 to 80 % of the CAM preparation comes from material costs and that these costs should not diminish due to learning effect or evolution but rather scaling up of production . The cost foresight exercise done uses different material cost shares to explore what we see as lower bound cost, ranging from around $\$100 kWh_{cell}^{-1}$ to $\$180 kWh_{cell}^{-1}$ of NCA storage capacity.

Building a PBCM on (Kwade *et al.*, 2018), (Duffner *et al.*, 2020) obtained a $\$106 kWh_{cell}^{-1}$ in the base case and a $\$64 kWh_{cell}^{-1}$ in the optimised case by using lever such as chemistry change (i.e. NCM622 to NMC811), labour cost, scrap rate reduction, increasing output, modification

of technical characteristic of the cell or the production line such as electrode thickness or stacking speed respectively.

Building on its previous work (Duffner, Krätzig and Leker, 2020) try to identify the cost-optimal location within the EU-28 considering labour cost, energy cost & other variables. They also try to consider knowledge expertise based on some values such as the number of relevant publications in the field, or the number of relevant graduates. The analysis leads to an apparently conflicting dimension between cost and knowledge:

Figure 8 Cost-knowledge matrix for the location of a battery cell plant in the European Union. (Duffner, Krätzig and Leker, 2020)

Some studies focus mainly on the energy side. (Weeber *et al.*, 2020) compare different locations by considering energy cost, energy greenhouse gas intensity and environmental conditions.

	Energy consumption $kWh\ kWh_{cell}^{-1}$			GHG in CO_2 -eq kWh_{cell}^{-1}			Cost of energy only $\$ kWh_{cell}^{-1}$		
	min	Avg	max	min	avg	Max	min	avg	Max
Germany	93	174	290	38,9	70,01	113,8	9,7	17,1	27,4
China	96	174	283	60	106,18	170,3	5,8	10,45	17
Sweden	101	193,5	328	8,9	19,23	35,1	5,9	11,15	18,7

Table 2 Results from Weeber et al (2020) simulation for energy only

A study inquires about the economies of scale that can be achieved within battery manufacturing by a PBCM. They focus on optimising the capacity of machinery along the whole cell production line to minimise the machinery idle time, change chemistry the energy density and adapt the cell production scale. It result in production costs ranging between \$98.1 and \$113.2 kWh_{cell}^{-1} for a NMC811 cell with a density of 0.198kWh/kg depending on the scale/idle capacity of processes (Mauler, Duffner and Leker, 2021).

According to (Turcheniuk *et al.*, 2021) raw material accounts for 50-65% of the LIB cell production cost, hence no substantial decrease can be expected if no new chemistry for active and inactive raw material enters the market. Since the 90s the maturation of the LiB market already led to an enormous decrease from a \$4500 to \$100-250 kWh_{cell}^{-1} . Although cheaper materials used in LFP or LMO lead to lower raw material prices, their energy density or the precursor preparation hamper the final cost-benefit. Moreover, the boomier future of raw materials supply for nickel or cobalt does not prequel lower prices or stability in the production cost of cells because of their lion's share in the final cost of a cell.

The manufacturing cost decomposition reported by the author for 2019 was the following:

Figure 9 Cost share per manufacturing step (Turcheniuk *et al.*, 2021)

The reported and expected overall price decomposition for a cell reported by the author for 2019 and 2030 was:

Figure 10 Cost structure of averaged LIB cells as a function of cathode chemistry in 2019 (the cell energy and energy density are indicated for completeness); (Turcheniuk *et al.*, 2021)

When looking at specific manufacturing steps slurry mixing or coating/drying (Schünemann *et al.*, 2016; Li *et al.*, 2017; Rohkohl *et al.*, 2022; von Drachenfels *et al.*, 2022; Ventura Silva *et al.*, 2023) was often a focus as it is the preliminary and its result greatly influenced the cell manufacturing cost (e.g. for the drying, the quality of the slurry) and the technical performances of a cell.

Figure 11 Manufacturing cost accumulation during electrode and cell manufacturing; upper graph: manufacturing cost, including material; lower graph: manufacturing cost, excluding material (Schünemann *et al.*, 2016)

A review of battery cost forecasting, with a focus on the pack level, by (Mauler *et al.*, 2021) looks at the different models, horizons, and levels (e.g. material, cell, pack...), they use surcharge rates of 30.89%, 33.51%, and 6.14 % for cell-to-pack, material-to-cell and electrode-stack-to-cell levels respectively. Out of the 51 publications dated from 2010 to 2021, we observe a decline in the cost projected hence following the cost observed at the date of publication, moreover, the bottom-up modelling (e.g. PBCM) is the most used method (i.e. Other being technological learning, literature-based-projection and expert elicitations).

We denote that some projections were accurate:

Figure 12 Forecasted values of studies applying technological learning methods to derive time-specific estimates. (Mauler et al., 2021)

(Jinasena, Burheim and Strømman, 2021) develop a process-based model to compute energy consumption per kWh of cell produced and identify the main energy-consuming process. One important thing to note is the following graph:

Figure 13 Stacked diagram of applied cost layers for the production of NMC111-Gr prismatic cell in the US (black dashed line tracks the lowest price of the total battery cell cost).

Which highlight the scale-up effect but also its co-dependency with capacity capped activity requiring CAPEX such as machinery (i.e. the repeating spike).

Another study focused on cost and considering the location of the manufacturer (Orangi and Strømman, 2022) also ended with the share of the lion for the raw material followed by “Labour” or “Machinery and installation” depending on the location. The capital invested for machinery is also greater than any energy cost in every location, putting a highlight on the formation, dry rooms and coating & drying machinery.

(Hewawasam *et al.*, 2022) use BATPAC to analyse cost depending on the electrode coating thickness the result found a cost reduction (e.g. from 8% to 17.5% in case of thickness doubling) depending on the chemistry.

(Mauler *et al.*, 2022) looks at innovations from both active material and cell manufacturing technologies and end up with an optimist forecast for nickel-based chemistry with a cell production cost of $\$88.6 kWh_{cell}^{-1}$ for 2024.

A recent publication (Degen and Krätzig, 2023) reports that the raw material share of the total cost within a cell kept increasing, it is a logical consequence of the optimisation (i.e. reduction) of the manufacturing process, whereas cell manufacturing is reaching a level of maturity where the “out of hands” costs remain stable. Future large cost reductions should be expected from the raw material supplier despite the past showing that a threshold might have been reached in this sector.

(Bielewski *et al.*, 2023) also reported a share of the cell price increasing with respect to the final battery cost price:

Figure 7. Volume-weighted average Li-ion battery pack and cell price split (real terms 2022 USD/kWh, based on 178 data points from EVs, buses, commercial vehicles and stationary storage).

Source: BloombergNEF, Dec 2022

Figure 14 Volume-weighted average Li-ion battery pack and cell price split (real terms 2022 USD kWh_{cell}^{-1} , based on 178 data points from EVs, buses, commercial vehicle and stationary storage) (Bielewski *et al.*, 2023)

(Hasselwander, Meyer and Österle, 2023) collected different KPIs per chemistry, because the energy density is given at the cell level we will assume that the cost is also given at the cell level and in $\text{€ } kWh_{cell}^{-1}$:

	NMC-111	NMC-532	NMC-622	NMC-811	LFP	NCA
Literature		75–85	80–90	90–100 108	90 112	65–75 90 102
Expert	145 117–135	130 108–126	100 90–108	90 81–90	70–110 54–81	80–130 72–90
Model assumption	145	130	100	90	80	90

Table 3 Overview of the cost in $\text{€ } kWh_{cell}^{-1}$ of current cell chemistries considered within (Hasselwander, Meyer and Österle, 2023)

They also conclude that the rise of LFP could help lower the final price of xEV by up to 21% at an equal range.

In 2023 (Orangi *et al.*, 2023) analysed different raw material price prospective scenarios to understand the impact on the cell cost and concluded that high costs for the NCM market could impede the widespread adoption and that LFP could be the technology achieving the long-awaited price parity with ICEV and hence alleviating the previously quoted risk.

A focus on the “main” energy-consuming steps such as drying is done by (Schütte, Degen and Walter, 2024) to understand the benefit of switching technology for electrode drying, they end up with an energy-saving potential ranging from 50% to 80% for Near-Infrared-drying and laser-drying for the drying of the electrodes.

Just this year (Orangi *et al.*, 2024) highlighted that a cap of $\$75 \text{ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ at the cell level should be reached to render xEV more interesting than ICEV, they create complex scenarios accounting for the technical performative evolution of each production steps, the materials, scale, scrap rate and chemistry market share. They concluded with the graph which tries to explain the past and future savings on cell manufacturing:

Figure 15 Determinants for cost declines of LiBs and their contributions over (a) historical period, (b) projected period under the assumption of LFP market share scenario, and (c) projected period under the assumption of NCX market share assumption. (Orangi *et al.*, 2024)

As you can notice most of the expected cost decline from non-material reason, technology enhancement (Use rate of machinery, better energy density, less scrap) , economic (reduce labour & overhead cost).

5.4. Environmental assessment

A review (Peters *et al.*, 2017) find that for the LCI published between 2000 and 2015' the environmental footprint range between 40 to 270 kg CO₂-eq kWh_{cell}⁻¹ (average of 110) produced with an energy demand ranging from 56 to 694 kWh/kWh_{cell}⁻¹ (average of 328) produced. Electricity consumption, with cradle-to-gate approach, is the main driver identified for GHG emissions.

In the simulation, as cited before, (Weeber *et al.*, 2020) simulate a 0.23GWh battery manufacture in three locations Germany, China and Sweden are modelled to consider meteorological contexts, energy production mix and energy costs the gate-to-gate approach identifies:

	Energy consumption kWh / kWh_{cell}^{-1}			GHG $CO_{2eq} / kWh_{cell}^{-1}$		
	min	avg	max	min	avg	Max
China	63	174	283	60	70	170.3
Germany	93	174	290	38.9	106.2	113.8
Sweden	101	193.5	328	8.9	19.2	35.1

Table 4 Total energy demand per kWh of cell capacity (Weeber *et al.*, 2020)

Some publications focus on energy use within the manufacturing process (Weeber *et al.*, 2020; Degen and Schütte, 2022; Kallitsis, 2022) as it is often stated as the “most” influential for the GWP impact category. The first of them tries to highlight the fact that a comparison of energy intensity should be done considering the chemistry, the final product (e.g. cell or pack, with a preference for cell), a strict definition of the supply chain involved (e.g. with/without the active material synthesis as there is a tendency to integrate this part of the process) and the scale of production.

A three-dimensional life cycle assessment of an NMC811-Gr cell done by (Gutsch and Leker, 2024) proposes results of $\$94.5 kWh_{cell}^{-1}$, $64.5kgCO_{2eq} kWh_{cell}^{-1}$, an energy (gas and electricity) intensity of $55.4 kWh kWh_{cell}^{-1}$ and a single value called combined environmental impact with no interest to us here due to its computation, contextuality and subjectivity.

In 2020, (Sun *et al.*, 2020) computed an LCA of the production of an NCM622-Gr at the cell level for 6 impact categories of the CML-IA baseline V3.02 (e.g. PED, GWP, AP, POCP, EP & HTP). The IA is separated into “Material” and “Production”, production starting at the manufacturing of the electrode (hence without the precursor). Among these 6 categories, the greatest contributor is always the material (with an 85% minimum share), when diving into production-related impacts then the steps of “Coating and drying” and “Vacuum drying” always come out first.

Figure 16 Relative contributions of per kWh NCM 622 battery production. (Sun *et al.*, 2020)

The contribution to GWP for material and production was evaluated to 105.47 and 19.01 kg CO₂-eq.

In 2022, (von Drachenfels *et al.*, 2022) obtained an LCA score per impact category of a NCM622-Gr cell ($0.2252 kg kWh_{cell}^{-1}$ energy gravimetric density), each cell manufacturing

steps including the impact of the material introduced in the process, its findings show the total domination of the “Cathode dry and wet mixing”, “Cathode coating and drying”, “Anode dry and wet mixing” and “Anode coating and drying” which consolidate the major role of electrode material within the GWP.

Figure 17 E-LCA of an NMC622-Gr (von Drachenfels et al., 2022)

In 2022 (Degen and Schütte, 2022) modelled another PCM while taking into account the energy mix and share of energy emerging from gas or electricity, surprisingly the heat used in some of their process (e.g. formation) is more interesting when supplied by gas than electricity in some countries due to the high GHG intensity of the electricity supply mix. They also report a range from 10.33 to 157.44 kgCO₂eq kWh_{cell}⁻¹ for cell production (excluding material) and energy consumption of 28.72 to 117.22 5 kWh kWh_{cell}⁻¹.

(Chordia, Nordelöf and Ellingsen, 2021) assess the production of two battery cell (i.e. NMC111 & NMC811), by retaking from (Ellingsen et al., 2014), updating the background database and modifying it to represent a giga-factory (based on Northvolt environmental permit) with more up-to-date data the GWP expressed in kgCO₂eq kWh_{cell}⁻¹ for cell production fell from 188 to 109 even though only updating the background data led to a rise of 45 kgCO₂eq kWh_{cell}⁻¹. These updates led the material to take again responsibility for a great part of the GWP, acidification and human health-related ICs.

(Dai et al., 2019) also found out that more than 80% of every impact category such as Total energy use, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, NOx emissions, SOx emissions, PM emissions, and water consumption come from materials. Moreover, the materials with the highest impact per kWh of NMC111 battery were the NMC111 powder (5 out of 6) and aluminium (1 out of 6) :

Figure 18 Cradle-to-gate impact breakdowns and bill of materials (BOM) of 1 kWh NMC111 battery. Blue denotes material inputs; orange denotes energy inputs for cell production. (Dai *et al.*, 2019)

(Bouter and Guichet, 2022) did a statistical review of papers published between 2015 and 2019 and assemble more than 377 observations out of 32 publications (with (Ciez and Whitacre, 2019) accounting for 216 due to the use of a monte carlo simulation) and derive a median in $\text{kgCO}_2\text{eq kWh}_{\text{cell}}^{-1}$ for 4 chemistry, 72.5 for NMC, 73.5 for LFP, 74.1 for LMO and 41.7 for NCA.

(Kallitsis *et al.*, 2023) led a general study with a focus on location and material, with a common basis on material they ended-up with a [50-180] $\text{kgCO}_2\text{eq kWh}_{\text{cell}}^{-1}$ for a cradle-to-gate assessment, when accounting only for material then the median values for NMC111, NMC622, NMC811, NCA and LFP are 64.3, 56.1, 47.4, 47.8 and 28.3 $\text{kg CO}_2\text{-eq kWh}_{\text{cell}}^{-1}$ for a cell of given capacity.

5.5.Scrap

(Wessel *et al.*, 2021) cite up to 40%, or even up to 80% according to newspapers during startup periods (*Panasonic and Tesla factory scrap half a million batteries a day, 2019; The good news about battery production scrap, 2022; Battery Plant Scrap Rates Can Hit 90% at Ramp Up, but the Situation is Improving, 2024*). However, a more serious range is said to be 6%, 10% and up to 30% for the best producers, for the typical producer and finally for the startup period of the producer respectively (Gaines *et al.*, 2021). (Duffner *et al.*, 2020) state that 5% of finished cells do not conform to quality requirements.

(Orangi *et al.*, 2024) collected a scrap rate from 2010 to 2024 and proposed a scenario until 2030, ranging from 30% to 1% passing by the 10.8% in 2023 based on the fact that manufacturer are improving their process.

The reasons for this scrap rate can be multiple, from unfitted raw material input (e.g. copper foil that needs to be cut), destructive testing (Taking a sample out of the process to test it.), high standard quality testing and complexity of the process with many steps (up to 25 depending on the battery design).

Other studies indirectly approach battery manufacturing scrap under a specific scope such as quality testing (McGovern *et al.*, 2023), and non-destructive testing more precisely to allow the production to “flow” more easily and avoid scrap due to poor quality or destructive testing. Moreover, it is known that even if quality tests are passed by lithium cell, they are further ranked into rank A, B and C, destining them to different usage.

5.6. Social-LCA

The S-LCA guidelines and tools mentioned in section 4.6 have already been applied in the published research, covering different battery chemistries. Both PSILCA and SHDB have recently been identified as the available databases to determine social impacts in S-LCA of batteries (Cellura *et al.*, 2024).

(Koese *et al.*, 2023) performed a cradle-to-use S-LCA on LIB (Lithium-Ion Battery) vs. VRFB (vanadium redox flow battery) systems, using the PSILCA v.3 database. Lithium manganese oxide (LMO) and nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC111) cathodes were considered for LIB, and product systems located in Germany and China were compared. (Popien *et al.*, 2023) limited their study to three specific SHDB subcategories (risk of child labour, risk of forced labour, and risk of corruption). They analysed ten different batteries for electric vehicles including NMC622, applying a cradle-to-gate scope and considering the component production in China and battery production in Germany. Similarly, (Barke *et al.*, 2021) evaluated the risk of child labour, risk of forced labour, and risk of corruption using the SHDB for eight battery systems (NMC and LFP among others). The SHDB was also the basis for exploring the social risk profile of LFP (Lithium–iron phosphate) battery production in China, Japan and South Korea, with a cradle-to-gate scope (Shi *et al.*, 2023). (Thies *et al.*, 2019; Thies, Kieckhäfer and Spengler, 2021) used the SHDB for the social sustainability assessment of NMC-G cell chemistry (the CAM is lithium-nickel-manganese-cobalt oxide and the AAM is graphite). The implications of mineral price volatility on the outcome of S-LCA modelling have been recently investigated (Orola, Uusitalo and Levänen, 2024), using the SHDB to compare NMC 811 CAM production in Finland vs. globally.

Social LCA methodologies have also been applied in European projects, but very few on the topic of batteries deliver publicly available reports. STORY project applied a cradle-to-gate scopus to assess lithium-ion batteries for energy storage applications based on the UNEP/SETAC guidelines. However, no comprehensive S-LCA was conducted due to a lack of information (STORY, 2020). BAMLIT aimed to develop a new organic redox flow battery and built a S-LCA approach with cradle-to-use scope following the UNEP/SETAC guidelines, using the PSILCA database and impact assessment method (BAMLIT, 2023).

5.7. Conclusion

From a cradle-to-gate perspective, cell social, environmental and economic impacts are dominated by processes led upstream of the cell manufacturing process. Mining, refining, chemical compound or active material preparation are the most impact full, this is even more true for Nickel and cobalt-based chemistry. Whereas cathode material was often the focus, different pathways for graphite, natural and synthetic, have shown large share in different IC's.

Keeping in mind the BATMACHINE scope, thus not considering a drastic change in cell chemistry or the chemical used, energy consumption during the manufacturing process

must be dissected. Currently, energy consumption during drying steps for cathode and anode, final steps for cell preparation such as ageing or formation through the operation of Environmental temperature-controlled rooms (e.g., dry rooms), and dryers take the largest share. Moreover, both at the cost and environmental level, scrap avoidance or recovery of solvent can bring valuable benefits.

Expected cost reduction in literature will also arise from energy saving, making energy saving of the utter most importance for a sustainable and economical cell manufacturing. Hence, actions that can be done on steps toward a more sustainable cell manufacturing will both bring saving and improve the environmental performance of cell manufacturing.

Finally the social LCA is in its infancy but assessment often points out child-labour, corruption and forced-labour due to the supply chain of raw material or manufacturing in country with less stringent rule of law.

6. Pomega production line

The information provided by Pomega that can contribute to the cost assessment are the following:

- Cell characteristics
- Material cost
- Quantity of materials needed
- Amount of energy (e.g. Only electricity here)
- Losses per material (and not step)
- Hours of worker

6.1. Environmental life cycle assessment

6.1.1. Results

The below shows the environmental impacts of the manufacturing of the Pomega LFP-100Ah Ah cell, per kWh capacity.

Impact category	Value	Unit
acidification accumulated exceedance (AE)	9,00E-01	mol H+eq
climate change global warming potential (GWP100)	9,35E+01	kg CO2 eq
ecotoxicity: freshwater comparative toxic unit for ecosystems (CTUe)	1,22E+03	CTUh
energy resources: non-renewable abiotic depletion potential (ADP): fossil fuels	1,04E+03	ADP
eutrophication: freshwater fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	8,07E-02	kg Peq
eutrophication: marine fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	1,59E-01	kg Neq
eutrophication: terrestrial accumulated exceedance (AE)	1,22E+00	mol Neq
human toxicity: carcinogenic comparative toxic unit for human (CTUh)	1,17E-07	CTUh
human toxicity: non-carcinogenic comparative toxic unit for human (CTUh)	5,87E-06	CTUh
ionising radiation: human health human exposure efficiency relative to u235	3,30E+00	kBq U235
land use soil quality index	3,94E+02	N.A
material resources: metals/minerals abiotic depletion potential (ADP): elements (ultimate reserves)	5,17E-03	kg Sbeq
ozone depletion ozone depletion potential (ODP)	5,90E-06	kg CFC-11eq
particulate matter formation impact on human health	1,87E-05	Disease incidences
photochemical oxidant formation: human health tropospheric ozone concentration increase	3,68E-01	kg NMVOCeq
water use user deprivation potential (deprivation-weighted water consumption)	4,56E+01	m3 world eq. deprived water

Table 5 E-LCA result with EF3.1 for Pomega cell LFP-100Ah

The energy consumption associated with the manufacturing of 1kWh of battery within Pomega is 34.127 kWh kWh_{cell}^{-1} which is in the lowest bound both in quantity (Weeber *et al.*, 2020) as 72.5 kWh kWh_{cell}^{-1} is cited by (Lai *et al.*, 2022), 37.5 kWh kWh_{cell}^{-1} by (Degen *et al.*, 2023).

This is good news, as even when Pomega is not fully calibrated because it did not reach full-scale production, the energy intensity of their cell production is in the lowest band of identified energy consumption for LFP cells.

Even when comparing with other chemistry at the GWh scale, the range of 30-50 kWh kWh_{cell}^{-1} identified by (Kallitsis, 2022), place the energy density of the cell production in the lowest part of the range.

The climate change impact, equal to 93.5 kgCO₂eq kWh_{cell}^{-1} is close to (Lai *et al.*, 2022) that obtain 85.5 kgCO₂eq kWh_{cell}^{-1} for a cell manufacturing happening in China. As most of it depends on the material, the updated source we used for graphite might be the reason as the GWP is 4-5 times higher compared to natural graphite and nearly three times higher for natural graphite compared to Ecoinvent Dataset.

When accounting only for GHG emission due to the energy use within the production facility we end up with 19.59kgCO₂-eq, with a GHG intensity of 0.57 kgCO₂-eq kWh^{elec} .

Figure 19 Contribution to GWP per process step for Pomega LFP 100Ah
 Every production step on this figure, that is readable, has an exogenous material as input, obviously the active material for both mixing part, but also aluminium and copper for the coating, electrolyte for the filling, separator for the stacking and the prismatic housing for the Pair-cutting step

Figure 20 E-LCA score with EF3.1 for Pomega LFP 100Ah cell

The picture here is more diverse, as always Anode and Cathode mixing part dominate but the step “Cell A: Filling” also plays a big part because of the electrolyte being accounted for within this step.

6.2. Economic assessment

Despite the presence of material losses, their direct association with scrap is done just for exploration purposes *as they cannot be associated to scrap after discussion*. However, extrapolating real scrap values from the literature is not done due to the detailed data about the Pomega manufacturing process (i.e. 24 steps) which could lead to a more misleading conclusion.

6.2.1. Results

The evaluation of the cost was done for 1 kWh of LFP 100Ah (i.e. 6.20 kg with an energy density of $0.160 \text{ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$) led to an estimate of $78.63\text{€ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$, an estimate which includes material, labour and cost for electricity within Türkiye.

The losses of material as described in the annexes are included in the material cost compartment, and not the scrap, an assessment where no losses have also been done leading to a cost of $70.95\text{€ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ hence saving up to 7.68€ or 9.8% could be achieved.

Figure 21 Cost share per modelled compartment of LFP100 Ah 3.2V cell from Pomega

The second scenario accounts for material losses and assigns them to the material cost compartment will be the one used from now on as losses are not equal to scrap.

(Wentker, Greenwood and Leker, 2019) which proposes an estimation of the cell LFP-Gr (i.e. with a gravimetric density of $0.220 \text{ kWh}_{cell}^{-1} \text{ kg}$) material cost equal to 84.8, 78.9, 67.3 and $\$55.0 \text{ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ for factories of yearly output capacity of 1, 2, 8, and 35GWh respectively. When comparing to the 1 GWh, a material cost of $84.8 \text{ € kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ along with the 31% of CAM result in 26.24\$, which is slightly lower than the 29.26€ from our computation which in turn represents 39.4% of the total material cost.

Possible explanations include the difference in energy gravimetric density of the Pomega LFP-Gr cell with a density of $0.160 \text{ kWh}^{-1} \text{ kg}$ versus the $0.211 \text{ kWh}^{-1} \text{ kg}$ of (Wentker, Greenwood and Leker, 2019) or the difference in non-cathode-related material cost such as the separator.

Figure 22 Pomega material cost share

The contribution of each material within the cost material compartment lets us denote the high share of the CAM, electrolyte, graphite and separator as this master thesis found out (Alva, 2023). However, the proportion taken by the Electrolyte is close by a than expected,

By reusing cost compartment cells at the cell level of (Duffner *et al.*, 2020) for an NMC811-Gr cell with the “Optimised scenario” and the one of (Orangi *et al.*, 2024) for an LFP-Gr cell, we can rebuild the final cost of the cell.

We selected the “Optimised scenario”¹(Duffner *et al.*, 2020), and the scenario of the year 2024 for the LFP-Gr cell (i.e. energy density of $0.201 \text{ kWh}_{cell}^{-1} \text{ kg}$ and cost of $\$75.1 \text{ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$) of (Orangi *et al.*, 2024) and we retrieve the following cost compartment share:

¹ Depreciation of building and maintenance have a share of the cost of 0.5% instead of 1% so that all the cost compartment share sum up to 100.0%.

Figure 23 Cost share used to compute Pomega production cost

We can compare the cost share by recomputing their relative cost share based on the only 3 or 4 compartments computed in our case, we can see the results are pretty close.

Figure 24 Relative share between cost compartments computed

To obtain an estimate of the production cost of the cell in € kWh_{cell}^{-1} we divide the sum of the cost compartment from our computations by the sum of the cost share for the accounted compartment from the other scenario and obtain the following :

Figure 25 Reconstructed kWh_{cell}^{-1} cost in € based on (Duffner *et al.*, 2020; Orangi *et al.*, 2024)

We end up with the following costs for (Duffner *et al.*, 2020) :

Optimised case	Duffner et al, 2020
-----------------------	----------------------------

Cost compartment	Losses as material cost	Losses as scrap
Depreciation building	0,40 €	0,43 €
Maintenance	0,40 €	0,43 €
Energy	2,42 €	2,60 €
Overhead	2,42 €	2,60 €
Scrap	4,84 €	5,19 €
Labor	1,61 €	1,73 €
Depreciation machine	6,45 €	6,92 €
Material	62,09 €	66,63 €
Total cost	80,64 €	86,54 €

Table 6 Cost assessment result for GIGAGERMA based on Duffner et al., 2020

And with the following costs for (Orangi et al., 2024) :

LFP-Gr, 2024	Orangi et al, 2024		
Cost compartment	Reference	Losses as material cost	Losses as scrap
Depreciation building	0,18 €	0,24 €	0,26 €
Maintenance	1,06 €	1,40 €	1,52 €
Energy	2,55 €	3,38 €	3,68 €
Overhead	4,13 €	5,46 €	5,94 €
Scrap	4,39 €	5,80 €	6,32 €
Labor	1,44 €	1,91 €	2,08 €
Depreciation machine	10,55 €	13,96 €	15,20 €
Material	45,26 €	59,87 €	65,20 €
Total cost	69,56 €	92,01 €	100,20 €

Table 7 Cost assessment result for Pomega based on Orangi et al, 2024

Depending on the accounting method of waste we end up with a cost of 80.64, 86.54, 92.1 and 100.20 $\text{€kWh}_{\text{cell}}^{-1}$.

For comparison the original result obtained by (Orangi et al., 2024), named as Reference, have been added.

6.2.2. Conclusion

Despite the lack of data, a preliminary analysis could be done, leading to a material cost that lies in the expected range [55.0 ,84.8] $\text{\$kWh}_{\text{cell}}^{-1}$ for (Wentker, Greenwood and Leker, 2019). Even when looking at the total cell production [80,100] it correspond to the [75.1,105.7] $\text{\$kWh}_{\text{cell}}^{-1}$ from (Duffner et al., 2020), [90,112] from literature, [70,110] and [54;81] from experts and 80 $\text{\$kWh}_{\text{cell}}^{-1}$ from a model (Table 3 Overview of the cost in $\text{€ kWh}_{\text{cell}}^{-1}$ of current cell chemistries considered within (Hasselwander, Meyer and Österle, 2023)).

The use of diverse cost compartment share could be pertinent in the next analysis but LFP cost studies are often scarce, even more at the process level.

Based on the fact that Pomega is still in the scaling-up process and that some additional steps might come online such as NMP recovery, we can expect lower production costs in the future. The LFP 100Ah production line is efficient and will probably propose a cell at a

competitive price, moreover, as it is not the only type of cell that will be produced, the raw material price might also decrease due to the larger quantity needed.

To achieve the 5% expected cost reduction one should focus on scrap or material losses as mentioned above which already represent more than 9% or change of material used within the manufacturing process.

6.3. Conclusions for targets

	Value related	Value
KPI 3.2: Energy efficiency of the cell manufacturing increased by at least 20%	Energy consumption per kWh storage capacity of cell manufactured	34.127 kWh kWh_{cell}^{-1}
KPI 3.3: The production costs of cell manufacturing decreased by at least 5%	Production cost of the cell manufacturing per kWh storage capacity	[92-100]€ kWh_{cell}^{-1}
KPI 3.4: Integration of renewable energies to supply the manufacturing of batteries with a minimum reduction of 15 % of GHG	GHG emissions associated with the energy consumption of the cell manufacturing per kWh of storage capacity	19.59kgCO ₂ -eq
KPI 4.1: Sustainable by design: the implementation of eco-design measures, including early-phase LCA, and S-LCA, should lead to a decrease in greenhouse gas emissions of at least 15%.	GHG intensity per kWh at cell-level production	93.5 kg CO ₂ -eq kWh_{cell}^{-1}
KPI 4.2: Quantify 16 different environmental impact categories of which 50% will decrease.	16 ICs have been quantified with EF3.1 methodology.	See Table 5.
KPI 4.3: Social benefits for the whole society in terms of impact in economic wealth, as well as on the creation of new jobs	N/A	N/A

All these values will be added to the reference set of values used to compute the progress within each KPI. The values computed for KPI 3.4, 4.1 and 4.2 are not a range and hence contain a lots of uncertainties, depending both on the foreground and background data. The KPI 4.3 associated with the social LCA will be taken into account later on in the project for the POMEGA manufacturing line.

We hope that further down the project a more refined version of the dataset collected by Pomega will be made available which will enhance all dimensions of the LCA assessment.

7. GIGAGERMA production line

The information provided by GIGAGERMA that can contribute to the cost assessment are the following:

- Cell characteristics
- Quantity per material (NMC622 precursor) or type of material (Solvent, binder, conductive additive etc..)
- Amount of energy for some step(e.g. Only electricity here)

7.1. Environmental life cycle assessment

7.1.1. Results

Impact category	With losses	No losses	Unit
acidification accumulated exceedance (AE)	1,40E+00	8,99E-01	mol H+eq
climate change global warming potential (GWP100)	1,51E+02	9,99E+01	kg CO2 eq
ecotoxicity: freshwater comparative toxic unit for ecosystems (CTUe)	2,30E+03	1,46E+03	CTUh
energy resources: non-renewable abiotic depletion potential (ADP): fossil fuels	2,13E+03	1,42E+03	ADP
eutrophication: freshwater fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	9,24E-02	6,39E-02	kg Peq
eutrophication: marine fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	2,65E-01	1,70E-01	kg Neq
eutrophication: terrestrial accumulated exceedance (AE)	1,81E+00	1,17E+00	mol Neq
human toxicity: carcinogenic comparative toxic unit for human (CTUh)	9,91E-07	6,24E-07	CTUh
human toxicity: non-carcinogenic comparative toxic unit for human (CTUh)	6,34E-06	4,11E-06	CTUh
ionising radiation: human health human exposure efficiency relative to u235	2,29E+01	1,53E+01	kBq U235
land use soil quality index	5,44E+02	3,56E+02	N.A
material resources: metals/minerals abiotic depletion potential (ADP): elements (ultimate reserves)	1,08E-02	6,88E-03	kg Sbeq
ozone depletion ozone depletion potential (ODP)	4,79E-05	3,01E-05	kg CFC-11eq
particulate matter formation impact on human health	2,88E-05	1,82E-05	Disease incidences
photochemical oxidant formation: human health tropospheric ozone concentration increase	5,86E-01	3,79E-01	kg NMVOCeq
water use user deprivation potential (deprivation-weighted water consumption)	3,80E+02	2,39E+02	m3 world eq. deprived water

Table 8 E-LCA result with EF3.1 for GIGAGERMA cell DE-89 with Notching losses

If we avoid the losses of the notching step, the result falls from 151 to 99 kgCO₂-eq, which is probably closer to the real case. This decrease of 52 kg CO₂-eq, or 35%, lets us know that

most of the contribution to the GWP happens before the notching, which is where the raw material for both electrodes is accounted.

The energy consumption happening on the manufacturing site is responsible for 11,86 and 10,881 kgCO₂-eq, corresponding both to less than 10% of the overall GWP impact category.

According to the literature, the cradle-to-gate GWP of the NMC622-Gr cell should be of the following magnitude 58 kg CO₂-eq kWh_{cell}⁻¹ for (von Drachenfels *et al.*, 2022), 105.47 and 19.01 kg CO₂-eq kWh_{cell}⁻¹ by (Sun *et al.*, 2020) for material and cell manufacturing respectively, 56.1 kg CO₂-eq kWh_{cell}⁻¹ for (Kallitsis *et al.*, 2023), 56.4 and 52.3 kg CO₂-eq kWh_{pack}⁻¹ for the baseline and the manufacturing in Europe case (Winjobi, Kelly and Dai, 2022).

Most of these values are lower than the result we obtained, this might be because the Natural Graphite Dataset used is up to 3-5 times higher than the one from Ecoinvent and up to 10 times Synthetic Graphite(e.g. They were seemingly underestimated before (Engels *et al.*, 2022; Carrère *et al.*, 2024))

Both energy consumption are in the lowest bound or largely smaller than values found within the literature being, 26.83 kWh kWh_{cell}⁻¹ for an NMC622-Gr reported by (Degen *et al.*, 2023) reported, 30.6,41.5 and 50 kWh kWh_{cell}⁻¹ for NMC622-Gr reported by (Kallitsis, 2022), 41.48 kWh kWh_{cell}⁻¹ of NMC622-Gr cell for (Degen and Schütte, 2022) , 32.1 kWh kWh_{cell}⁻¹ of NMC622-Gr Pouch cell (with an energy gravimetric density of 0.225 kWh/kg) from (von Drachenfels *et al.*, 2022). (Lai *et al.*, 2022) obtain 64.63 kWh kWh_{cell}⁻¹ for an NMC622 cell, 29.44 kWh kWh_{cell}⁻¹ from (Sun *et al.*, 2020). Some literature differs for the energy consumption (SI: Sun *et al.*, 2020, tbl. 6) estimate the energy consumption of NCM 622 cell manufactured to 106 kWh kWh_{cell}⁻¹ of which 67% are electricity.

Future assessments should not only be based on energy consumption as all other information comes from external sources and the bill of material influences more than 70% of the GHG impact. Considering other dimensions such as scrap, or basic technical parameter improvement w.r.t change within the manufacturing process could improve cell manufacturing.

An analysis per step was done for the scenario with no losses at the notching step, and every material impact was assigned to the process taking it as input :

Figure 26 Contribution to GWP per process step for GIGAGERMA DE-89 without notching losses

What can be noticed here is the large share of the two mixing parts, including the CAM and AM. More than 80% is taken by both mixing part. Overall, for each IC for each process

step was also generated, still highlighting the high contribution of electrode AM, electrolyte (Filling) or aluminium/copper foil (Coating).

Figure 27 E-LCA score with EF3.1 for GIGAGERMA DE-89 with no notching losses

The prevalence of the Cathode and Anode materials impact is true for in every impact category.

7.2. Economic assessment

7.2.1. Results

The evaluation of the cost was done for 1 kWh of DE-89 (i.e. 4.63 kg with an energy density of $0.216 \text{ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$) led to an estimate of $90.64 \text{ € kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$, an estimate which includes material and cost for electricity within Germany.

Figure 28 Total cost of the DE-89 cell from GIGAGERMA

Figure 29 Material cost share of GIGAGERMA

When looking in detail at the material cost we see a huge share, greater than 50%, originate from the cathode active material, which is in line with (Greenwood, Wentker and Leker, 2021) who propose a CAM > 60% for an NMC622-Gr cell, the anode represent 13.3% whereas it takes >16% in (Greenwood, Wentker and Leker, 2021) Again the cost we have for our separator is about 38€kg⁻¹ which is more than a hundred time greater than the 0.33\$kg⁻¹ used in their assessment, however, BatPac3.1 use a similar price of 79.71\$kg⁻¹. The large difference leads to, alas, “large” uncertainty in the cost assessment.

The 54.98\$ kWh_{cell}⁻¹ of material cost obtained by in (Greenwood, Wentker and Leker, 2021) is about 30\$ cheaper than our BoM despite the common source for the NMC-622 precursor. The gravimetric energy density of their NMC622-Gr cell is 30% higher (282.16 vs 212 Wh kg⁻¹), which could also imply a price difference of 30% without accounting for Price difference in Separator for example

We selected two scenarios:

- The “Base case scenario”² from (Duffner *et al.*, 2020) which represents an NMC622-Gr cell with an energy density of 0.265 kWh_{cell}⁻¹ kg and a cost of \$106 kWh_{cell}⁻¹
- The scenario of the year 2024 for the NMC622-Gr cell (i.e. energy density of 0.242 kWh_{cell}⁻¹ kg and cost of \$94.2 kWh_{cell}⁻¹) of (Orangi *et al.*, 2024)

The compartment used to recompute the total production cost of the cell is the following:

Figure 30 Cost share used to compute GIGAGERMA production cost

When following the same attribution methodology used within the Pomega case, hence by assigning the known cost (e.g. Material and energy) to their respective share.

We can recompute the total cost and respective value of each unknown compartment:

² Depreciation of building and maintenance have a share of the cost of 0.5% instead of 1% so that all the cost compartment share sum up to 100.0%.

Figure 31 GIGAGERMA cost share for manufacturing of one kWh of DE-89 cell

We end up with the following costs with (Duffner *et al.*, 2020) scenario :

Optimised Scenario	Duffner et al, 2020			
	Reference	No losses	With losses	Losses as scrap
Cost compartment				
Depreciation building	0,94	1,51	2,23	2,00
Maintenance	1,89	3,02	4,47	4,00
Energy	1,89	3,02	4,47	4,00
Overhead	5,67	9,07	13,41	12,01
Scrap	6,61	10,58	15,64	14,01
Labor	7,56	12,09	17,88	16,01
Depreciation machine	15,11	24,17	35,76	32,02
Material	54,78	87,63	129,62	116,08
Recomputed total	94,44	151,08	223,49	200,14

Table 9 Cost assessment result for GIGAGERMA based on Duffner *et al.*, 2020, value in $\text{€kWh}_{\text{cell}}^{-1}$

We end up with the following costs with (Orangi *et al.*, 2024) scenario:

LFP-Gr 2024	Orangi et al, 2024			
	Reference	No losses	With losses	Losses as scrap
Cost compartment				
Depreciation building	0,17	0,23	0,34	0,31
Maintenance	0,82	1,10	1,62	1,49
Energy	2,10	2,81	4,16	3,82
Overhead	3,21	4,30	6,37	5,84
Scrap	6,16	8,26	12,21	11,19
Labor	1,08	1,44	2,13	1,95

Depreciation machine	8,18	10,97	16,23	14,88
Material	65,49	87,84	129,93	119,08
Recomputed total	87,19	116,95	173,00	158,56

Table 10 Cost assessment result for GIGAGERMA based on Orangi et al., 2024, value in €kWh_{cell}^{-1}

Depending on the cost compartment shares used the production cost varies between $[151.08, 223.49] \text{€ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ and $[116.95, 173] \text{€ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ based on (Duffner et al., 2020) and (Orangi et al., 2024) respectively. The large difference observed is because the two case studies have a final cost & share per compartment difference, for example just for material the difference is 17% mainly because they are different materials.

7.2.2. Conclusion

The costs are not comparable to the ones found and are way higher than expected, this leads to huge cost differences with current estimations from (Duffner et al., 2020) or (Orangi et al., 2024).

Moreover, the energy density used in the two based scenario, are way higher 0.265 and 0.242 $\text{kWh}_{cell}^{-1} \text{ kg}$ versus the 0.216 $\text{kWh}_{cell}^{-1} \text{ kg}$ for the GIGAGERMA cell.

This range, $[116.95, 223.49] \text{€ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ could belong to the small-scale manufacturer that GIGAGERMA is, and we do not take into account here the lifecycle or other technical characteristics of the battery that could differentiate the product from its concurrent.

The shares taken by machinery and energy is 16% and 2% within (Duffner et al., 2020) and 2.48% and 9.38% within (Orangi et al., 2024) do not predict that huge cost reduction can be achieved by sole change of machinery for a given step such as Slurry mixing or calendaring as planned within the BATMACHINE project.

In order to achieve the 5% expected in cost reduction one should focus on scrap reduction or change of material used within the manufacturing process.

The range $[116.95, 173] \text{€ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$ seems to be the most realistic due to the current price of NMC622-Gr cell.

7.3. Social LCA

After setting the goal and scope, the supply chain composition was defined by describing how the production costs are distributed among the manufacturing steps by CSS (Country-specific sectors); i.e., how costs are allocated to each sector/country pair.

The main steps followed for the S-LCA presented herein consisted of:

1. Collection and analysis of primary data from GIGAGERMA and secondary data sources, to identify the production cost breakdown by CSS.
2. The SHDB was used in SimaPro to allocate the production cost breakdown (in USD) to the corresponding social LCI dataset for every CSS.
3. The impact assessment was conducted to identify the social hotspots for social categories and subcategories in the cell manufacturing process.

7.3.1. Inventory operational Inputs

Materials, energy and water consumption

Data on material, energy and water amounts were provided by GIGAGERMA on the different manufacturing steps, and Europe and Asia were specified as the origins of some

of the materials. However, due to confidentiality reasons, the specific chemical composition and countries of origin were unknown in some cases. Therefore, secondary data was considered to complete the social LCI.

Data about potential countries of origin and largest material suppliers were obtained from sources provided by WP6 (Road-mapping and Adaptation to the Future Technologies), specifically:

- Processed materials and components with unknown origin were assumed to be supplied by China, Japan, or South Korea, according to (Huisman *et al.*, 2020) (Figure 34). This consideration was also applied to the electrolyte, which was purchased from Asia.

Figure 32. Li-ion batteries: key players along the supply chain. Extracted from (Huisman *et al.*, 2020).

- Cathode binders and Anode conductive additives, which were specified to be obtained from European suppliers by GIGAGERMA, were assumed to be supplied by Belgium, Germany, or France. Both the information in Figure 34 and additional data on potential suppliers provided by WP6 were considered in this assumption.
- The Separator was assumed to be obtained from Japan, South Korea, or Germany, according to additional data on potential suppliers in WP6.

It was assumed that the origin of intermediate products and scrap was the location of GIGAGERMA facilities (Germany). The data collected is presented in the annexes.

7.3.2. Calculations and assumptions to identify the production cost breakdown

As previously described, the specific composition of some of the material inputs was unknown (i.e. binders, additives, and electrolytes). Therefore, it was not possible to perform a detailed calculation based on each raw material price to determine the production cost breakdown. Only a detailed calculation of the energy costs of each process was done, and the rest of the cost breakdown was estimated according to literature information.

The DE-89 Energy Cell production cost breakdown was estimated based on the literature:

- (Orangi and Strømman, 2022): Total costs of cells: NMC622G 90-150 USD/kWh, depending on different factors such as raw materials and labour costs, or the factory production capacity.
- (Duffner *et al.*, 2020): Base scenario considered is NMC622G @ 35 GWh annual factory capacity in Germany. Total production cost is 106 USD/kWh. Cost share: 58%

materials, 16% machine depreciation, 8% labour, 7% material scrap, 6% overhead, 2% energy, 2% maintenance, and 1% building depreciation.

- (Hasselwander, Meyer and Österle, 2023): Total costs of NMC622 cells: 100 EUR/kWh using a model assumption based on the literature review followed by four expert interviews. By converting EUR to USD in 2023, it corresponds to 106 USD/kWh (with an average exchange rate 1.0824 USD, and worst exchange rate 1.0468 USD).

Hence, **the total cell cost considered was 106 USD/kWh** (Duffner *et al.*, 2020; Hasselwander, Meyer and Österle, 2023), and the cost production breakdown followed the share proposed by (Duffner *et al.*, 2020). It is expressed both in percentage and absolute values in USD for the functional unit in Table 11.

Table 11. Overall cost share considered for the S-LCA presented in this report

Share (%) ref. (Duffner <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Share (USD/kWh)
Material (EX)	58
Energy	2
Rest (IN, S)	40
Total	100

(Wentker, Greenwood and Leker, 2019) modeled a total cost of materials of 62,47 USD/kWh for NMC622G (CellEst model; 8 GWh annual factory capacity), and provided the component cost breakdown. These components correspond to the materials identified as exogenous products (EX) in our case study, so we used their cost share with a correction factor considering our total cost of 61,48 USD/kWh.

The total energy costs estimated (2,12 USD/kWh) were distributed among the manufacturing steps including electricity and natural gas as operational inputs, according to the energy amounts specified by GIGAGERMA. Water was finally disregarded given its low consumption in the manufacturing process and usual costs which would result in negligible cost share.

The rest of the production costs (42,40 USD/kWh) were distributed equally among the 14 inputs designated as intermediate or scrap products. These costs would be associated to steps taking place in GIGAGERMA's plant and would be covered by the rest of the elements in the case study (Duffner *et al.*, 2020): machine depreciation, labour, material scrap, overhead, maintenance, and building depreciation.

Detailed calculations to obtain material and energy cost breakdown by manufacturing process are provided in the tables below.

Table 12. Energy cost breakdown calculations based on primary data from GIGAGERMA. Price of electricity in Germany in 2023 was 0,266 USD/kWh, and the price of natural gas was 0,104 USD/kWh [3].

Step ID	Input	Energy consumption [kWh]	Cost [USD]	Cost share corrected to 2,12 [USD/kWh]
TOTAL		7,36	1,47	2,12

Table 13. Overall breakdown calculated for Materials, energy, and rest of production costs, based both on primary data from GIGAGERMA and secondary data from the literature.

[3] Available at: <https://es.globalpetrolprices.com/Germany/> Last accessed: 13 June 2024.

Step ID	Material UID	Cost share [USD/kWh] in 2023			
		Materials share from reference (Wentker, Greenwood and Leker, 2019)	Materials share corrected to 61,48 USD	Energy share	Rest (IN, S)
Cathode manufacturing-Slurry mixing	Cathode Active Material Li (Ni0.6 Mn0.2 Co0.2)O2	27,07	26,64		
	Cathode Binder 1	1,10	1,08		
	Cathode Binder 2				
	Cathode Conductive Additive 1	0,32	0,31		
	Cathode Conductive Additive 2				
Electricity			0,01		
Anode manufacturing-Slurry mixing	Anode Active Material Graphite	11,17	10,99		
	Anode Binder 1	1,10	1,08		
	Anode Binder 2				
	Anode Conductive Additive 1	0,32	0,31		
	Anode Conductive Additive 2				
Electricity			0,01		
Cathode manufacturing-Coating	Aluminium Foil	1,30	1,28		3,03
	Cathode slurry				
	Electricity				
Anode manufacturing-Coating	Copper Foil	3,55	3,49		3,03
	Anode slurry				
	Electricity				
Cathode manufacturing-Electrode Drying	Cathode coated				3,03
	Natural gas				
Anode manufacturing-Electrode Drying	Anode coated				3,03
	Natural gas				
Cathode manufacturing-Calendaring	Cathode dried				12,11
Anode manufacturing-Calendaring	Anode dried				
Cathode manufacturing-Notching	Cathode calendared				
Anode manufacturing-Notching	Anode calendared				

Step ID	Material UID	Cost share [USD/kWh] in 2023			
		Materials share from reference (Wentker, Greenwood and Leker, 2019)	Materials share corrected to 61,48 USD	Energy share	Rest (IN, S)
Cell manufacturing-Lamination	Cathode notched				6,06
	Anode notched				
	Separator	11,19	11,01		
Cell manufacturing-Assembly	Electrodes laminated				3,03
	Pouch Foil	1,32	1,30		
	Tab				
Cell manufacturing-Drying	Cell assembled				3,03
	Electricity			0,38	
Cell manufacturing-Electrolyte filling	Cell dried				3,03
	Electrolyte	4,03	3,97		
Cell finishing-Ageing & Formation	Cell with electrolyte filled				3,03
	Electricity			1,04	
TOTAL		62,47	61,48	2,12	42,40

7.3.3. Data modelled using SHDB in SimaPro

The SHDB is based on the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) global economic equilibrium model version 9, using 2011 as the primary reference year. Thus, all the cost values provided in Table 13 were adjusted for inflation to USD 2011 using the same tool as (Koesse *et al.*, 2023), and the total cost of 106 USD/kWh was converted to 81,15 USD/kWh. The final cost share and CSS modelled for the manufacturing steps of the cell produced by GIGAGERMA are presented in Table 14 below.

Table 14. Final LCI data on Materials, energy, and rest of production costs, and CSS assigned using SHDB in SimaPro. “CHN” and “JPN” represent CASE 1 and CASE 2 proposed in section 11.4.6

Step	Operational inputs	Cost breakdown [USD 2011]	SHDB Sector
1. Cathode manufacturing-Slurry mixing	1.1. CAM	20,40	Metal products (fmp)/CHN S vs. JPN S
	1.2. Binders	0,83	Chemical, rubber, plastic products (crp)/DEU S
	1.3. Conductive additives	0,24	Chemical, rubber, plastic products (crp)/CHN S vs. JPN S
	1.4. Electricity	0,01	Electricity (ely)/DEU S
2. Anode manufacturing-Slurry mixing	2.1. AAM	8,42	Petroleum, coal products (p_c)/CHN S vs. JPN S
	2.2. Binders	0,83	Chemical, rubber, plastic products (crp)/CHN S vs. JPN S
	2.3. Conductive additives	0,24	Chemical, rubber, plastic products (crp)/DEU S
	2.4. Electricity	0,01	Electricity (ely)/DEU S

Step	Operational inputs	Cost breakdown [USD 2011]	SHDB Sector
3. Cathode manufacturing-Coating	3.1. Aluminium Foil	0,98	Metals nec (nfm)/CHN S vs. JPN S
	3.2. Cathode slurry	2,32	Manufactures nec (omf)/DEU S
	3.3. Electricity	0,09	Electricity (ely)/DEU S
4. Anode manufacturing-Coating	4.1. Copper Foil	2,67	Metals nec (nfm)/CHN S vs. JPN S
	4.2. Anode slurry	2,32	Manufactures nec (omf)/DEU S
	4.3. Electricity	0,09	Electricity (ely)/DEU S
5. Cathode and Anode manufacturing-Electrode Drying	5.1. Cathode and Anode coated	4,64	Manufactures nec (omf)/DEU S
	5.2. Natural gas	0,34	Gas manufacture, distribution (gdt)/DEU S
6. Cathode and Anode manufacturing-Calendar and Notching	6.1. Cathode and Anode dried and calendared	9,27	Manufactures nec (omf)/DEU S
7. Cell manufacturing-Lamination	7.1. Cathode and Anode notched	4,64	Manufactures nec (omf)/DEU S
	7.2. Separator	8,43	Chemical, rubber, plastic products (crp)/DEU S
8. Cell manufacturing-Assembly	8.1. Electrodes laminated	2,32	Manufactures nec (omf)/DEU S
	8.2. Pouch Foil and Tab	0,99	Metals nec (nfm)/CHN S vs. JPN S
9. Cell manufacturing-Drying	9.1. Cell assembled	2,32	Manufactures nec (omf)/DEU S
	9.2. Electricity	0,29	Electricity (ely)/DEU S
10. Cell manufacturing-Electrolyte filling	10.1. Cell dried	2,32	Manufactures nec (omf)/DEU S
	10.2. Electrolyte	3,04	Chemical, rubber, plastic products (crp)/CHN S vs. JPN S
11. Cell finishing-Ageing & Formation	11.1. Cell with electrolyte filled	2,32	Manufactures nec (omf)/DEU S
	11.2. Electricity	0,79	Electricity (ely)/DEU S

7.3.4. Results

The two Life Cycle Impact Assessment Methods offered with the SHDB were used in SimaPro to calculate the social impacts for the cell manufacturing process:

- The Social Hotspot 2021 Category Method with Weights (SHI 1), which weights the main impact categories equally.
- The Social Hotspot 2021 Subcategory Method with Weights (SHI 2), which weights the impact subcategories equally.

Weighting methods from SHDB were selected based also on those applied on previous research (Shi *et al.*, 2023; Cellura *et al.*, 2024; Orola, Uusitalo and Levänen, 2024).

The SHI method combines the labour-intensity information with the social risk levels to express social risks and opportunities in terms of medium risk hours equivalent (Mrheq), using characterisation factors (low/medium/high/very high risk). These factors enable to determine a total quantity of risk in Mrheq for each indicator and identify which CSS and which social inventory flows contribute how much of the total risk for each indicator,

pointing to hotspots. Finally, the risks are aggregated across categories and subcategories to calculate a social footprint (single impact indicator: Pt).

Overall social impacts on stakeholder categories

In terms of the stakeholder categories, the main findings from the assessment were:

- Both in CASE 1 and CASE 2, **2.Health & Safety** social category is the most impacted by the cell manufacturing process, followed by the **4.Governance** category.
- When comparing the alternative origins considered, social **impacts of CASE 1-China are more than twice of CASE 2-Japan.**

Social impacts on stakeholder categories per manufacturing step

Concerning the different manufacturing stages of the cells studied:

- In CASE 1-China, the most important contributions to social hotspots were found for the Cathode manufacturing in the Slurry mixing step. The Cathode Active Material is the operational input with greatest impact.
- In CASE 2-Japan, a relevant social hotspot was found for the Cell Lamination process, where the Separator operational input poses the main contribution to the impact.

Overall social impacts on stakeholder subcategories

Considering the stakeholder subcategories, it was found that in line with the results using the SHI 1 (Category) method:

- **Subcategories within 2.Health & Safety** and **4.Governance** categories would be the most impacted by the cell manufacturing process. In addition, some subcategories in **1.Labor Rights & Decent Work** category were observed to be significantly impacted.
- After the weighting step, when comparing the alternative origins considered, social **impacts of CASE 1-China are more than twice of CASE 2-Japan.** Keeping this in mind, in both cases specific subcategories belonging to 2.Health & Safety category showed the greatest relevance in terms of social footprint. Specifically, the most important impacts (sorted from highest to lowest) for each case were:
 - CASE 1-China
 - 2.A Occupational Toxics & Hazards (2,57E+16 Pt)
 - 2.B Injuries and Fatalities (1,91E+16 Pt)
 - 1.E Forced Labor (1,78E+16 Pt)
 - 1.K Discrimination and equal opportunity (1,70E+16 Pt)
 - 4.C Democracy & freedom of speech (1,59E+16 Pt)
 - CASE 2-Japan
 - 2.B Injuries and Fatalities (1,08E+16 Pt)
 - 1.E Forced Labor (8,12E+15 Pt)
 - 2.A Occupational Toxics & Hazards (7,50E+15 Pt)
 - 1.K Discrimination and equal opportunity (7,02E+15 Pt)
 - 1.F Excessive Working Time (5,31E+15 Pt)

Social impacts on stakeholder subcategories per manufacturing step

The same remarks presented for stakeholder categories apply for the impacts of the manufacturing processes on the social subcategories: In CASE 1-China the CAM has the greatest impact, whilst in CASE 2-Japan the Separator poses the main contribution to the impact.

Interpretation

The studies reported in the literature addressing S-LCA on NMC622G batteries comprehensively are still scarce. However, similar recommendations for LIB production can be proposed in general terms based on the social hotspots identified.

In a comparison of product systems located in Germany and China, (Koese *et al.*, 2023) observed that:

- Most social risks were associated with the raw material extraction stage, while sectors related to chemicals also entailed considerable risks.
 - Similarly in the present study, social hotspots were found for exogenous products classified into the SHDB sectors: Metal products CHN vs. JPN (CAM), Petroleum, coal products CHN vs. JPN (AAM), and Chemical, rubber, plastic products DEU (Separator).
- Workers were the stakeholder group most affected. These results applied to supply chains located in both China and Germany, but risks were lower for similar supply chains in Germany.
 - In the present study, categories and subcategories linked to workers showed the highest impacts both in CASE 1-China and CASE 2-Japan: “2.Health & Safety” category and “2.A Occupational Toxics & Hazards”, “2.B Injuries and Fatalities”, and “1.E Forced Labor” subcategories.
- LIB containing cobalt (NMC111 cathode) was associated with considerably larger risks compared to cobalt-free LIB (LMO cathode), which was mainly due to cobalt mining in Congo.
 - This is widely known in the batteries community and can be useful in terms of recommendations for LIB production and the developments proposed in BATMACHINE.

(Popien *et al.*, 2023) considered the component production in China and battery production in Germany, and their assessment was limited to three specific SHDB subcategories (risk of child labour, risk of forced labour, and risk of corruption):

- For LIB-NMC622, the risk of forced labour showed the highest score among the three subcategories considered.
 - This would be consistent with the results obtained in the present study. Although we analysed the 30 SHDB subcategories and higher risks were observed for other subcategories, “1.E Forced Labor” subcategory was also among those three most impacted both in CASE 1-China and CASE 2-Japan.
- Amongst all the components and battery production steps, the CAM (produced in China) had the major contribution to social impacts on the three subcategories analysed.
 - The same was observed in the present study for CASE 1-China, in which the CAM operational input was modelled to be produced in China.

(Barke *et al.*, 2021) associated the highest social risks of the different LIB variants (NMC-111, NMC-442, NMC-532, NMC-622 and NMC-811) with cathode's electrode paste production, which was explained by the extraction and processing of nickel and cobalt. (Shi *et al.*, 2023)] identified significant concerns regarding corporate social compliance in the production of LFP batteries, emphasising the need for greater corporate responsibility and transparency in supply chains, particularly in China, Japan, and South Korea.

A recent literature review on social LCA of batteries supply chains concluded that raw material extraction and processing were the riskiest stages (Koese *et al.*, 2023). Workers were the stakeholder group most analysed, with the recurring impact category on work conditions. It highlighted the necessity of more research and objective analyses to clearly quantify the impacts from the life cycle stages, and to allow comparisons among different scenarios.

Looking at the European battery ecosystem, recent publications by Batteries Europe support also the findings presented in this report:

- Position Paper on Sustainability (BEPA, Adam Cooper, *et al.*, 2024). It underscores the difficulties in the interpretation of the results in S-LCA methodology, because often the uncertainties are higher than the differences of the compared options. However, imported materials currently overshadow European production, often linked to social issues like child labour and inadequate occupational safety particularly in raw material production.

- In their Position Paper on SSH (BEPA, Marcel Weil, *et al.*, 2024), four case studies were explored to illustrate the integration of SSH into the batteries agenda. Those addressing S-LCA of batteries had already been mentioned in the present report: (Koesse *et al.*, 2023; Shi *et al.*, 2023). This document proposed some research gaps and questions remaining in SSH batteries research, which are in line with the results presented in this deliverable: the socio-environmental impacts of the expanding battery industry and rare mineral mining in Europe, and more effective integration of SSH into battery-related policies to address issues of resource ethics and material neo-colonialism.

The JRC project SureBatt linked to the European Commission’s RMIS-Raw Materials Information System proposed recommendations for designing batteries considering responsible sourcing of batteries raw materials (*RMIS - Responsible sourcing*, no date). The objective was to detect potential criticalities in the materials value chain, thus using country-based data (PSILCA database) to identify countries that could be at risk. A hotspot analysis was applied to the supply of primary raw materials used in batteries, considering cobalt, lithium, nickel, manganese and natural graphite. In the case of cobalt, Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) alone provides around 60% of the global supply. Results confirmed that DRC was, by far, the country at highest risk, especially concerning conflict, child labour, forced labour and governance. The assessment of responsible sourcing initiatives for cobalt provided a non-exhaustive list of responsible sourcing initiatives and strategies (detailed information on the promoters available in the link (*RMIS - Responsible sourcing*, no date):

- Cobalt Industry Responsible Assessment Framework (CIRAF)
- Sustainable procurement framework for Cobalt
- Responsible Cobalt Initiative
- The Responsible Minerals Initiative
- Clean Cobalt Framework
- Better Mining
- Mutoshi Pilot Project
- Cobalt for Development

Sensitivity analysis

Finally, a sensitivity analysis was conducted focusing on the origin of operational inputs and the greatest social impacts, which were observed in CASE 1-China for the Cathode Active Material. A **CASE 3-Germany** (“DEU” in SHDB modelling) was considered as an alternative with less social impact, taking into account that Europe is one of the key players in the market mix of processed materials and components (Huisman *et al.*, 2020). The Slurry mixing **cathode manufacturing** process was modelled based on the data provided in Table 15 and the Social Hotspot 2021 Category Method with Weights (SHI 1) was used.

Table 15. LCI data and CSS assigned using SHDB in SimaPro. “CHN” and “DEU” represent CASE 1 and CASE 3.

Step	Operational inputs	Cost breakdown [USD 2011]	SHDB Sector
1. Cathode manufacturing-Slurry mixing	1.1. CAM	20,40	Metal products (fmp)/CHN S vs. DEU S
	1.2. Binders	0,83	Chemical, rubber, plastic products (crp)/DEU S
	1.3. Conductive additives	0,24	Chemical, rubber, plastic products (crp)/CHN S vs. DEU S
	1.4. Electricity	0,01	Electricity (ely)/DEU S

The results obtained are shown in Table 16 and Table 17 (with text highlighted in grey corresponding to the highest impacts), and represented for each social category in Figure 33.

Table 16. Social impacts on stakeholder categories in CASE 1-China and CASE 3-Germany for process 1 - Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing, expressed in Mrheq.

Impact category	Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing - Case 1 (Mrheq)	Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing - Case 3 (Mrheq)
1 Labor Rights & Decent Work	20,71	6,05
2 Health & Safety	34,69	10,67
3 Society	15,29	3,44
4 Governance	30,73	7,44
5 Community	13,09	3,83

Table 17. Social impacts on stakeholder categories in CASE 1-China and CASE 3-Germany for process 1 - Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing expressed in Pt (after the weighting step in SimaPro).

Impact category	Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing - Case 1 (Pt)	Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing - Case 3 (Pt)
1 Labor Rights & Decent Work	2,93E+14	8,55E+13
2 Health & Safety	8,53E+16	2,62E+16
3 Society	1,37E+16	3,09E+15
4 Governance	4,07E+16	9,85E+15
5 Community	1,43E+16	4,19E+15
Total	1,54E+17	4,35E+16

Method: Social Hotspot 2021 Category Method w Weights / Equalcategoryweights / Weighting / Excluding long-term emissions
 Comparing 21,5 USD 2011 1. Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing (CHN) with 21,5 USD 2011 1. Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing (DEU);

Figure 33. Social impacts on stakeholder categories in CASE 1-China and CASE 3-Germany for process 1 - Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing expressed in Pt.

It was observed that the cathode slurry mixing for CASE 3-Germany impacted also the most on 2.Health & Safety social category, followed by the 4.Governance category.

When comparing the alternative origins considered, social impacts of CASE 3-Germany (4,35E+16 Pt) are less than one third of CASE 1-China (1,54E+17 Pt). However, the **impacts in CASE 2-Japan** were found to be **the lowest** (2,28E+16 Pt, see section 0).

7.3.5. Conclusions

The impact assessment conducted showed that 2.Health & Safety and 4.Governance were the social categories most affected for the two case studies considered, but social impacts of CASE 1-China were more than twice of CASE 2-Japan. When looking at the stakeholder subcategories (SHI 2 method), the results were aligned to a certain extent with those obtained from the Category method (SHI 1). Thus, subcategories within 2.Health & Safety and 4.Governance were amongst those most impacted, although some subcategories in 1.Labor Rights & Decent Work category were significantly impacted as well. Specifically, the three greatest impacts both for CASE 1-China and CASE 2-Japan were found at the same subcategories: 2.A Occupational Toxics & Hazards, 2.B Injuries and Fatalities, and 1.E Forced Labor. Concerning the manufacturing process of the cells, the same results were obtained when applying SHI 1 and SHI 2 methods. The most important contributions to social hotspots for CASE 1-China were found in the CAM manufacturing (Slurry mixing step), whilst in CASE 2-Japan, the Separator operational input (Cell Lamination step) posed the main impact.

In the interpretation phase it was found that although the literature addressing S-LCA on NMC622G batteries comprehensively is still scarce, similar recommendations can be proposed to optimise the social sustainability of the state-of-the art LIB cell production line. Based on the social hotspots reported both in previous and in the present study, the CAM operational input poses the greatest risks when comparing product systems in different potential locations, especially for workers and supply chains located in China.

The sensitivity analysis conducted to estimate the influence of the CAM input coming from China showed that the social impacts could be significantly reduced considering Germany as an alternative origin, but Japan would perform the best on social sustainability optimization.

8. Deviations

This deliverable was delayed due to late data collection from the manufacturing partner. Despite that, economic, social and environmental assessments were achieved in time. Moreover, instead of assessing all cell manufacturing lines of project partner only one, Pomega, was assessed. The assessment could not be done due to a soon-to-be-published sustainability report which will be disseminated to different stakeholder, hence any LCA of their production line could not be done as it could not reach the same conclusion. Difficulties have led to an assessment somehow limited but fills the information gap and will allow us to have a groundwork to assess the KPI and their evolution.

9. Conclusions

The economic and sustainable assessment review allowed us to identify current and common crucial steps for battery manufacturing, both within the manufacturing of cells and upstream. This pinned down some crucial steps in the cell manufacturing process such as anode drying, formation and ageing due to their energy consumption (heat, or electricity) from dryers or ambient controlled rooms.

The economic assessment review revealed the different form of models used, both for prospective and current production lines. New process-based models allowed to measure the possible improvements brought by technical improvements at precise steps of cell manufacturing. The ranges are often pretty close, the future expected benefit will lead to marginal benefit compared to past savings. One of the reasons is the gap closing to the threshold set by the material prices and components. Future benefits will hence not repeat the passed 90% saving but should in a rather reasonable range lower if no cheaper material is used. Cost savings are expected in energy saving mainly through the same manufacturing steps that are impactful within the environmental assessment.

The sustainability assessment done for the project partner Pomega led to positive conclusion, despite being in the starting period their cradle-to-gate assessment is in the best-in range for GHG with $93.5 \text{ kg } CO_{2eq} \text{ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$. The future integration of ReS, NMP recovery and optimisation of the energy consumption is expected to further bonify these results. Pomega production cost evaluation also led to state-of-the-art value of [80.64,100.20] € kWh_{cell}^{-1} .

For our European cell producer archetype, environmental assessment led to average impact for GHG with $99 \text{ kg } CO_{2eq} \text{ kWh}_{cell}^{-1}$, overall due to the raw material. On a gate-to-gate basis, the energy consumption is in the lower range and the use of water as an electrode solvent greatly reduces the environmental impacts. Production cost assessment show us a high range of value [116.95,223.49] € kWh_{cell}^{-1} , mainly due to the raw material cost which are subject to high-uncertainty due to the source used and poor data available. The social assessment highlighted the social impact category “Health and safety”, “Labour rights and decent work” along “Governance” were the hotspots of the social assessment, the contribution was associated to the cathode active material with a decisive criterion on the content of Nickel or Cobalt.

10. References

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11. Annexes

11.1. Methodology

11.1.1. Social

The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) defines the Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) as a methodology to assess the social impacts of products and services across their life cycle (e.g., from the extraction of raw material to the end-of-life phase, e.g., disposal) (Programme, 2020). It offers a systematic assessment framework that combines quantitative as well as qualitative data. S-LCA provides information on social and socio-economic aspects for decision-making, in the prospect to improve the social performance of products, processes and organizations, and ultimately the well-being of stakeholders. In terms of social metrics in international law and global policy, there are four common standards used in practice:

- Universal Declaration of Human Rights: proclaimed by the United Nations General Assembly in 1948. It establishes fundamental human rights to be universally protected and is widely recognized as having paved the way for the adoption of more than seventy human rights treaties.
- OECD guidelines on labour standards and economic integration, to govern working conditions.
- ILO labour standards, developed by the International Labour Organization since 1919, are essential in the international framework for ensuring that the growth of the global economy provides benefits for all.
- Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), 17 internationally agreed goals by all UN Member states to be reached by 2030.

In addition, the standard ISO/FDIS 14075 Environmental Management — Principles and Framework for Social Life Cycle Assessment is currently under development (ISO, 2024). It will cover for goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment, interpretation and reporting of S-LCA of a product (ISO, 2024).

Standards are all based on an international consensus among a wide majority of countries, but there is still more strict regulation and implementation of them in more developed countries.

Furthermore, on 23 February 2022, the European Commission adopted a proposal for a Directive on corporate sustainability due diligence (European Commission, 2024). The aim is to foster sustainable and responsible corporate behaviour and to anchor human rights and environmental considerations in companies' operations and corporate governance, including value chains inside and outside Europe. As of 2023 major companies are obliged to perform due diligence on Human rights and other topics throughout the value chain.

In the context of societal implications and human dimensions of battery technologies, the Batteries Europe/BEPA Task Force on Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) has recently presented their position paper (BEPA, Adam Cooper, *et al.*, 2024). It underscores the limited presence of SSH experts in the battery sector and advocate for the integration of SSH insights across the entire value chain of battery technologies. They call to action to stakeholders, policymakers, and industry players, who must adopt a "human-centric paradigm," where SSH is not peripheral but integral to technological development. The task force envisions a future where technological advancements in batteries are synergistic with societal progress. In terms of social assessment, Batteries Europe considers that S-LCA should reach end customers to encourage choosing sustainable products, and the proposed eco-labels for batteries should include social traceability criteria based on S-LCA results (BEPA, Marcel Weil, *et al.*, 2024).

Methodological guidance on S-LCA

The first guidelines for S-LCA were launched by UNEP/SETAC in 2009 within the Life Cycle Initiative (ANDREWS *et al.*, 2009). The foreword included in the 2020 edition (Programme,

2020) states that since 2009, the practice of S-LCA has evolved from a small circle of academic practitioners to one including stakeholders from industry, policymakers, and businesses. However, the S-LCA methodology is still in its infancy, fragmented with general theoretical concepts for which empirical data are widely missing. The framework provided by the UNEP/SETAC guidelines is under an agreement and standardization process, with indicators explicitly defined for different case studies. The indicators proposed so far are often assessed based on qualitative information rather than quantitative, given the nature of the social aspects under assessment. The position paper on Sustainability published by Batteries Europe (BEPA, Marcel Weil, *et al.*, 2024) highlighted also the fact that the S-LCA methodology is still on a development stage.

Moreover, the Social Value Initiative running from 2013 (PSIA, 2013), intends to be a cross-sector initiative to lead guidance on measuring the social impacts of products and services, in a way that is recognised for its quality, credibility and business viability. The Initiative was funded by different companies, with results and deliverables that are non-proprietary and available under a Creative Commons licence. The current Handbook for Product Social Impact Assessment (PSIA) (Goedkoop, de Beer, Harmens, visser, *et al.*, 2020) was published in 2020.

The main differences between the UNEP/SETAC and PSIA guidelines are found in the way they address the social metrics and topics. In terms of social metrics, UNEP/SETAC establishes five scale levels for social performance of the stakeholder groups. In the PSIA methodology, data about each social topic is interpreted with a scale considering dynamic evolution, and the generic scale is adapted for each social topic (Goedkoop, de Beer, Harmens, Morão, *et al.*, 2020).

The data collection strategy for the assessment is supported by different data sources available, where the most relevant categories are:

- (i) Primary or internal data: obtained directly from the value chains being analysed.
- (ii) LCA databases: using a common metric to describe social risks in a sector and/or company.
- (iii) Publicly available: with open access, such as national and global statistics organizations.

The Social Hotspots Database (SHDB) (*SHDB - Home*, no date) and PSILCA (Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment database) (Maister, 2020) are the main commercial databases available for modelling S-LCA, widely accepted by the LCA scientific community. Both PSILCA and SHDB are based on the stakeholder categories recommended in the UNEP/SETAC guidelines, and on global Input-Output databases with added social indicators. The SHDB offers the possibility of aggregation by calculating a single score (SHI), which is not available in PSILCA, where all the indicators are considered as equally important.

Recently, the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) published guidance for the voluntary application of 'safe and sustainable by design' (SSbD) framework for chemicals and materials (Commission *et al.*, 2024). This framework aims to support the design and development of safe and sustainable chemicals and materials with research and innovation activities. The socio-economic assessment is however an optional step in the SSbD framework, not included in the EC Recommendation, due to the lower methodological maturity of the related disciplines. The JRC guidance report proposes a simplified S-LCA to support the identification of potential social risks and opportunities within the supply chain of a chemical or material. Both PSILCA and SHDB are considered as the reference databases for the social inventory. For the impact assessment phase, an example is provided on the reference scale used to assess the indicators, based on the risk levels assigned by PSILCA.

The main data components of the SHDB involved in the different S-LCA phases are represented in Figure 36 (Commission *et al.*, 2024) and described in more detail below (Monique Bennema, Gregory Norris, and Catherine Benoit Norris, 2022).

Figure 34. The SHDB modular system: a Global input-output (IO) model (also called Multiregional Input-Output model or MRIO) for supply chain mapping; a Worker Hours Model for calculating a social footprint or handprint and identifying hotspots; and Data on social risks and opportunities by country and economic sector (country-specific sectors; CSS)

Supply chain composition

Knowledge of where the production activities are taking place is essential for social assessments because of the influence of societal, political, and cultural differences on the potential social impacts. The SHDB uses the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) global economic equilibrium model (Aguiar *et al.*, 2022, p. 11). GTAP is a global network of researchers and policymakers conducting quantitative analysis of international policy issues.

Labor intensity

Worker hours is the most popular activity variable in the literature that helps to identify where the human activity is occurring in supply chains. Worker hours play the same role as “elementary flows” in environmental LCA. SHDB developed the labor intensity data by dividing GTAP data on wage payments by the country and sector average wage. Thus, the worker hours are estimated for each sector (57) in each GTAP country/region for 1 USD of output. Thus, the SHDB can be used to identify how many worker-hours are involved for each unit process in the supply chain for a given final demand.

Social risks and opportunities and data quality

Publicly available information is collected in SHDB on over 160 social impact indicators for 244 countries and territories and 57 sectors. Data sources include intergovernmental databases, country statistics, NGO reports, Trade unions, and academic papers. For instance: The International Labor Organization, UNICEF, the World Health Organization, the U.S. Department of Labor, the U.S. Department of State, Eurostat, the World Bank are some of the sources used.

The determination of risk levels (characterization step) is based on data distribution, expert judgment, and literature. The characterization factors describe the severity of a serious situation or opportunity and facilitate data interpretation and visualization of results.

Social categories and subcategories

The database includes 160 indicators covering 30 impact subcategories, 6 impact categories, and 4 stakeholder groups: workers, local communities, value chain actors, and society. The social indicators and impact categories addressed by the SHDB are based on the international legal framework and social responsibility instruments and references (GRI, S-LCA Guidelines, ISO 26000, the Sustainable Development Goals). Table 18 lists the stakeholder categories and subcategories modelled in this study using SHDB in SimaPro.

Table 18. Social impact categories and subcategories covered by the SHDB impact assessment method and considered in BATMACHINE project.

SHDB categories	Impact	SHDB Impact subcategories
1 Labor Rights & Decent Work		1.A Wage Assessments
		1.C Workers in poverty
		1.D Child Labor
		1.E Forced Labor
		1.F Excessive Working Time
		1.G Freedom of Association, collective bargaining, right to strike
		1.H Migrant Labor
		1.I Social Benefits
		1.J Labor Laws & Conventions
		1.K Discrimination and equal opportunity
		1.L Unemployment
	2 Health & Safety	
		2.B Injuries and Fatalities
3 Society		3.A Indigenous Rights
		3.B Gender Equity
		3.C High Conflict Zones
		3.D Human Health Issues - Non-communicable diseases & other health risks
		3.E Human Health Issues - Communicable diseases
		3.F Poverty & inequality
		3.G State of environmental sustainability
4 Governance		4.A Legal System
		4.B Corruption
		4.C Democracy & freedom of speech
5 Community		5.A Access to Improved Drinking Water
		5.B Access to Improved Sanitation
		5.C Children out of School
		5.D Health Care System Access
		5.E Smallholders vs. Commercial Farms
		5.F Access to electricity
		5.G Property rights

Social Hotspot Index

Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) aims at evaluating and understanding the magnitude and significance of the potential impacts for a product system throughout its life cycle. The SHDB impact assessment method is called the Social Hotspots Index (SHI), and aggregates impacts for the entire supply chain.

The labor intensity information is used together with the social risk level to express social risks and opportunities in terms of medium risk hours equivalent (Mrheq), by sector and country for the social impact categories, subcategories, and the underlying indicators. Social impacts calculated in Mrheq provides a social footprint and identify target areas in supply chains to verify or improve social conditions (hotspots). This method conducts weighting, a step representing the relative probability of an adverse situation, by

augmenting or lowering the number of workers hours (medium risk hours or Mrh) depending on the risk level.

Table 19. SHDB Impact Assessment method: medium risk hour (Mrh) characterization factors.

Very High Risk	10
High Risk	5
Medium Risk	1
Low Risk	0.1

The weighting system considers the fact that the number of subcategories within each category and the number of indicators within each subcategory are not the same. There are two LCIA methods: the SHI 1 “SHDB Category method”, where the categories are all weighted equally, and the SHI 2 “SHDB Subcategory method” that weights the subcategories equally. In practice for the assessment, both methods are used.

11.2. Literature review

Due to industrial secrecy and high economic interest data on battery manufacturing is scarce, details are poor and even with a large amount of publications from grey literature data, verifiability can hardly be achieved leading to unsupported assumptions, however, with sometimes verified “market” price consequences.

A lot of the studies focus on nickel-based chemistry, only rare detail assessments for LFP production were found. The PBCM models (Duffner *et al.*, 2020, 2020; Duffner, Krätzig and Leker, 2020; Orangi and Strømman, 2022) used in many studies were not provided or scarcely described, both from the modelling point of view or from the parameter used. However they seem to offer detail, pertinent and highly customizable possibilities.

11.2.1. Cost

However one has to keep in mind that here the supply of material is not considered. Finally, EU policies such as the CRM Act, Battery Regulation Act or the expected Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism might also hamper the cost of LiB by raising their production cost in return for other benefits such as sovereignty or the rise of a sustainable environmental society.

For example, a CBAM with a €95/t applied on the import a really GHG intensity (e.g. 110 kg CO₂-eq kWh_{cell}⁻¹) could result in a 10,45 € increase, which is about both energy and labour cost summed. Hence considering GHG intensity could for price forecast or production cost could add significant difference to assessment.

It is worth noting that LFP-Gr battery prices are already below \$112 kWh_{pack}⁻¹ (LiFePO₄ Prices, 2024) and are expected to fall even below \$100 kWh_{cell}⁻¹ by 2024 within the Chinese market according to Benchmark Minerals’ monthly battery price tracker (Rocky Mountain Institute (RMI), 2023).

We can conclude that the manoeuvring capability of the manufacturer is rather low if no change of chemistry is involved, both for price or energy consumption.

However, some improvements have been highlighted multiple times, more than the upscaling factor which proposes a rather obscure way of improving manufacturing, certain technical progress such as dry coating, better dimensioning of dry room, scrap avoidance, reuse of solvent and replacement of material for a more sustainable and economic one still offers a large and diverse set-off improvements.

A definition of the production cost decrease for KPI 3.3 should be constrained under the fixed price of exogenous material hence no fluctuation could help achieve this price. When considering material cost in the production cost, the share remaining for other compartments such as energy or labour is low, this might prevent the achievement of the objective through a compartment different than “Exogenous material cost”.

11.2.2. Energy consumption

One of the awaiting improvements for cell manufacturing is the dry coating (Duffner *et al.*, 2020; Liu *et al.*, 2021; Aydin *et al.*, 2023; Orangi *et al.*, 2024), it will allow coating the foil with a nearly dry electrode paste hence saving on both slurry components such as the solvent but also minimising the drying part, often referred to as one of the most expensive.

Most often in literature, it is an improvement shortly expected, recently a lawsuit was filed where clues about a nearly or already readily available dry coating technology were being stolen (TESLA, INC., 2024)

The formation is also one of the most important steps for both energy consumption and cost due to its long time (e.g. and hence the need for space). The slow charging rate and sometimes repeated occurrence of charging instances within a specific atmosphere can lead to high energy consumption.

A definition of the energy efficiency should hence be frame under a gate-to-gate analysis and not consider upstream suppliers for KPI 3.2.

11.2.3. Outliers for energy consumption

Some largely quoted studies refer to really low energy consumption for the manufacturing, indicating or contradictory information with the current state of the art or a progressive increase in energy consumption of battery manufacturing per kWh of cell produced due to an increase in energy density.

For example (Li *et al.*, 2014, p. Table S18 Manufacturing of pouch cell) present a pouch-cell with a gravimetric energy density of 0,1241111111/kg, in the paper they refer to 144 prismatic cells with each a capacity of 98.55Wh (3.65V*27Ah), hence the total capacity is 14 kWh instead of the 43.2kWh declared.

In the case of (Richa, Babbitt and Gaustad, 2017), based on the information provided, a 24kWh battery composed of 192 cells of 819.85g each with a capacity of around 0.1524 kWh per cell. Then they decline the energy in the SI needed to manufacture the cathode, anode and finally cell (SI: Table 2,4 and 7), when summing up, with no correction except conversion of MJ to kWh, we end with around [5,6] kWh per kWh of cell produced which is 5 to 6 times smaller than the lowest estimate for gigafactory.

(Notter *et al.*, 2010) report a for 34kWh battery weighing 300 kg, with a cell share of the weight of 79,9%, we end up with a 0.141 kWh per kg of battery and manufacturing energy (Table S13, S14 & S16) of 2.26kWh per kWh of cell capacity.

Others, such as (Majeau-Bettez, Hawkins and Strømman, 2011) also end up with a really low energy consumption in kWh per kWh of energy produced, probably due to the proxy used, no further analysis could be done here due to the inaccessibility of the source used (Rydh and Sandén, 2005).

11.3. Pomega data

11.3.1. Process presentation & life cycle inventory scale

The data was provided on an average of 6 months while the factory was ramping up, moreover, it was provided at different granularity depending on the process group.

For the Anode and cathode preparation (e.g. From the slurry to the electrode ready to be stacked) the data was provided for the production of 750 LFP-Gr 100ah cells. The anode and cathode preparation steps are both composed of 6 sub-steps:

Figure 35 Pomega electrode manufacturing process steps

The subsequent 16 steps are all grouped under cell assembly:

Figure 36 Pomega cell manufacturing process steps

11.3.2. Energy consumption

For each of the 28 steps POMEGA provided energy consumption:

Process group	Step	Energy	Amount (kWh)
Cathode	Positive electrode mixing	Electricity	1135,00
	Coating of aluminium foil	Electricity	75,00
	Drying of the coated aluminium foil	Electricity	300,00
	Slitting of coated aluminium foil	Electricity	8,00
	Pressing the aluminium foil with a Roll Press	Electricity	40,00
	Slitting of the pressed & coated aluminium foil	Electricity	
Anode	Negative electrode mixing	Electricity	1135,00
	Coating of copper foil	Electricity	75,00
	Drying of the coated copper foil	Electricity	300,00
	Slitting of coated copper foil	Electricity	8,00
	Pressing the coated copper foil with a Roll Press	Electricity	40,00
	Slitting of the pressed & coated copper foil	Electricity	
Cell assembly	Die cutting & stacking	Electricity	1170,00
	Hot pressing	Electricity	75,00
	Pair Cutting & pre welding	Electricity	75,00
	Ultrasonic welding	Electricity	75,00
	Transfer sheet welding	Electricity	75,00
	Core closing and gluing	Electricity	75,00
	Mylar wrapping	Electricity	75,00
	Shell welding	Electricity	75,00
	Helium detection	Electricity	75,00
	Electrolyte filling	Electricity	75,00
	Formation	Electricity	75,00
	Neal welding	Electricity	75,00
	Second filling	Electricity	75,00
	Second Helium detection		
	Capacity grading		
	EOL tests		

Table 20 Pomega energy consumption per process per batch of 750 LFP cell 100Ah

Every step was also associated with a room where the step was “happening”, the steps had a duration hence we associated the duration of the step with the hourly consumption of the room. This is not a correct assumption as multiple steps can happen conjointly in the same room, however, due to a lack of information allowing us to do so we did not correct this assumption (Moreover the benefit of this consideration might be marginal)
 Please find below the room where each step takes place and the room's hourly energy consumption:

Room	Room hourly energy consumption (kWh)
Anode mixing	30
Cathode Mixing	40
Anode coating, slitting, roll press	45
Cathode coating, slitting, roll press	45
Anode Die-cutting	30
Cathode Die-cutting	35
Electrode Oven	25
Assembly Line	50
Electrolyte filling, formation	60
Aging room	30
Capacity Grading, End of line	30
Pack Line	30

Table 21 Pomega room hourly energy consumption

Process group	Step	Room	Duration
Cathode	Positive electrode mixing	Cathode mixing	300 minutes
	Coating of aluminium foil	Cathode coating, slitting, roll press	30 minutes
	Drying of the coated aluminium foil	Electricity	30 minutes
	Slitting of coated aluminium foil	Cathode coating, slitting, roll press	30 minutes
	Pressing the aluminium foil with a Roll Press	Cathode coating, slitting, roll press	30 minutes
	Slitting of the pressed & coated aluminium foil		30 minutes
Anode	Negative electrode mixing	Anode mixing	300 minutes
	Coating of copper foil	Anode coating, slitting, roll press	30 minutes
	Drying of the coated copper foil		30 minutes
	Slitting of coated copper foil	Anode coating, slitting, roll press	30 minutes
	Pressing the coated copper foil with a Roll Press	Anode coating, slitting, roll press	30 minutes
	Slitting of the pressed & coated copper foil		30 minutes
Cell assembly	Die cutting & stacking	Assembly line	180 minutes
	Hot pressing	Assembly line	180 minutes
	Pair Cutting & pre welding	Assembly line	180 minutes
	Ultrasonic welding	Assembly line	180 minutes
	Transfer sheet welding	Assembly line	180 minutes
	Core closing and gluing	Assembly line	180 minutes
	Mylar wrapping	Assembly line	180 minutes
	Shell welding	Assembly line	180 minutes
	Helium detection	Electrolyte filling, formation	180 minutes
	Electrolyte filling	Electrolyte filling, formation	180 minutes
	Formation	Electrolyte filling, formation	180 minutes
	Neal welding	Electrolyte filling, formation	180 minutes
	Second filling	Electrolyte filling, formation	180 minutes
	Second Helium detection	Electrolyte filling, formation	180 minutes
	Capacity grading	Capacity Grading, End of line	180 minutes
	EOL tests		180 minutes

Table 22 Pomega step duration

Finally, we have the information of each machine associated with the process, with their nominal capacity in technical terms (e.g. m/minute for coating or drying, volume for slurry mixer and product per minute for the cell assembly part), however, their direct association to energy consumption is obscure to us and could not help us to achieve finer analysis of the result or analysis, hence we did not considerate the energy consumption per machine but per step instead, which is fairly the same.

Identified anomalies within energy consumption are:

- Same electricity consumption per step for the group of anode/production process even though different solvents are used (NMP for cathode vs Water for Anode)
- Energy consumption for drying is really low and energy consumption for slurry mixing is strangely high
- Same electricity consumption for each step of the group of cell assembly except the Die cutting & stacking
- Die cutting & stacking present an energy consumption more than ten times higher than any other while it should not be one of the high points of consumption.
- Missing energy consumption for Second Helium testing, capacity grading, and EOL tests.
 - Grading should also have a high energy consumption
 - Moreover one step should at least consume electricity equal to at least one cycle of the 750 cells (244 kWh) due to the required energy for the formation

11.3.3. Material input, scrap rate, re-use and waste

	Step		Material	Amount	Unit
Cathode	Positive electrode mixing		LFP(Lithium phosphate) iron	500	kg
	Positive electrode mixing		SP(Conductive carbon black)	6	kg
	Positive electrode mixing		PVDF(Polyvinylidene fluoride)	10	kg
	Positive electrode mixing		CNT(Carbon nanotubes)	3	kg
	Positive electrode mixing		NMP(N-methylpyrrolidone)	250	kg
	Coating of alluminum foil		Aluminum foil	70	kg
Anode	Negative electrode mixing		Gr (graphite)	450	kg
	Negative electrode mixing		SP(Conductive carbon black)	5	kg
	Negative electrode mixing		CMC	8	kg
	Negative electrode mixing		SBR	10	kg
	Negative electrode mixing		Di-W	250	kg
	Coating of copper foil		Copper foil	120	kg
Cell assembly	Die cutting & stacking		Separator	3700	m2
	Pair Cutting & pre welding		Housing	750	pcs
	Electrolyte filling		Electrolyte	430	kg

Table 23 Material input for Pomega LFP 100Ah cell

Table 22

For each step material inputs were provided, and losses (which can be found next page) were subtracted at the input of the step:

Figure 37 Input (green) and waste (orange) of material per process step

Some preprocessing was done to convert material that was provided in different metrics to mass (e.g. Separator, housing, etc), if needed the computations can be provided.

As only losses per material were provided we assumed that each first step using this material was “losing” some and we did not distribute the weight of these losses along the steps. In our case, every material is used in only one step, putting the burden solely on this step.

After discussion with experts, losses differ from scrap rates and can happen due to different causes.

Material/Product	Waste Amount (%)
LFP(Lithium phosphate) iron	11
SP(Conductive carbon black)	11
PVDF(Polyvinylidene fluoride)	11
CNT(Carbon nanotubes)	11
NMP(N-methylpyrrolidone)	17
Aluminum foil	13
SBR	12
Gr (graphite)	12
CMC	12
Copper foil	14
Separator	8
Electrolyte	4
Housing	2

Table 24 Pomega waste amount per material

No information about scrap was given, for confidentiality reasons and because during the ramping up factory are known to have a high scrap rate. Some sources quote rates up to 30% during ramp-up and then up to 10% once the production stabilised.

No waste was provided even though some process uses water or NMP and recovery was pointed out by the manufacturer).

Identified anomalies :

- The final output must be equal to 750 cells of 2+-0.1kg or [1425;1575]kg.
- Mass balance :
 - No wastes are provided:
 - Slurry waste or evaporation at drying
 - If both electrode solvents with losses (i.e. 250kg of Water & 250 kg of NMP for Cathode, with 11% and 12% losses) are evaporated we end-up with 1575kg. Or an average weight of 2.1kg per cell, so at the maximum upper bound of their technical weight.
- The weight share of Cathode active material is at most 509 kg so just a bit above 33%
- The weight share of the Anode active material is at most 465 kg so just a bit above 31%
- No clear declaration of Current collector for both anode and cathode
- Some steps relate to material such as Mylar wrapping but the material was not declared as input (e.g. same for second filling which probably relates to a second electrolyte filling of the cell)

11.3.4. Economic assessment

Most of the material costs were provided by Pomega and come from China:

Material UID	Price	Price unit
LFP(Lithium phosphate) iron	12,5	€/kg
SP(Conductive black) carbon	7,3	€/kg
PVDF(Polyvinylidene fluoride)	11	€/kg
CNT(Carbon nanotubes)	4,7	€/kg
NMP(N-methylpyrrolidone)	3,1	€/kg
Aluminum foil	8,4	€/kg
SBR	6,4	€/kg
Gr (graphite)	5,3	€/kg
CMC	8,2	€/kg
Copper foil	11,5	€/kg
Separator	38,1 ⁴	€/kg
Electrolyte	5,1	€/kg
Housing	0,8 ⁵	€/pc
De-ionized water	0,0007	€/kg

Table 25 Material cost for the manufacturing of Pomega cell LFP 100 Ah 3.2V

Only one material cost was not provided, for de-ionized water and (Water Innovations, Inc., no date) was used, this simple proxy was used due to the low impact on the total cost of de-ionized water (i.e. It is used in the same quantity as CMC but up to 4 times cheaper). The price when compared to the one of Ecoinvent 3.10 updated to 2020 shows a difference of less than 5%.

The Turkish energy cost (i.e. only electricity here) was taken from (Eurostat, 2024a), and filtered based on the last 10 years (Second semester 2013 to 2023) and the price for Turkish electricity consumers of 20 MWh and above resulting in an average price of 0,0819€ kWh⁻¹.

The labour cost was only taken considering the step duration as a working hour of an employee as at least supervising might be needed.

The labour cost, 5.93€ h⁻¹, was taken from (Eurostat, 2024c) and filtered for the value corresponding to "Labour cost for LCI (compensation of employees plus taxes minus subsidies)", for the year 2023 and averaged for a subset of the following NACE-2 sectors:

- Professional, scientific and technical activities
- Manufacturing
- Industry (except construction)

These three sectors were taken because of the highly automated and skilled industry that is the battery industry.

⁴ Original price is 0,4€/m² conversion to kg was done considering 10.5g/m² (range provided is 8.5-12.5g/m²)

⁵ The housing include the tab and weight 100.43g pc⁻¹

This labour cost is comparable to the value of 5.27€ h⁻¹ for manufacturing provided by (Federal Statistical Office of Germany, 2021).

11.3.5. Environmental assessment

The background information used was :

Common name	LCI	ID or name	Source	Comment
Electricity mix		market for electricity, high voltage, TR	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
LFP precursor	LFP(Lithium iron phosphate)		Internal – Based on (Q. Dai et al., 2017)	
NMP	NMP(N-methylpyrrolidone)	N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone production, RoW	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
Carbon nanotube	CNT(Carbon nanotubes)	MWCNT	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122465 .	Multiwalled (MWCNT)
PVDF	PVDF(Polyvinylidene fluoride)	PVDF with route 1	10.1021/acssuschemeng.1c05350	
Graphite	Gr (graphite)		https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2022.130474	
Conductive carbon black	SP(Conductive carbon black)	market for carbon black, RoW	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
CMC	CMC	carboxymethyl cellulose production, powder, RER	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
SBR	SBR		Internal VUB	
Deionised-water	Di-W	water production, deionised, RoW	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
Aluminium-foil	Aluminum foil 14um	aluminium collector foil production, for Li-ion battery	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
Copper-foil	Copper foil 8 um	copper collector foil production, for Li-ion battery	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
Separator	Separator, PE and PP		Research project; internal FIVEVB	
Housing	Prismatic cell Housing Container Case		Research project; internal FIVEVB	Include current collector
Electrolyte	LiPF ₆ , EC, DMC	electrolyte production, for Li-ion battery, GLO	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	

Table 26 Exogenous material for the POMEQA manufacturing process

11.4. GIGAGERMA data

11.4.1. Process presentation & life cycle inventory scale

GIGAGERMA provided the data provided the data for the production of one DE-89 Energy Cell of 1.12 kg and an energy storage capacity of 0.216 kWh_{cell}⁻¹

The anode and cathode preparation steps are composed of 5 sub-steps :

Figure 38 GIGAGERMA electrode manufacturing process steps
The cell assembly step is composed of 5 sub-steps:

Figure 39 GIGAGERMA cell manufacturing steps

11.4.2. Energy consumption

GIGAGERMA provides the energy consumption, steps with no identified energy consumption were reported but no action was taken to solve the gap.

Process group	Step	Energy	Amount (kWh)
Cathode	Cathode slurry mixing	Electricity	
	Cathode coating	Electricity	
	Cathode electrode drying	Gas	
	Cathode calendaring	Electricity	
	Cathode notching	Electricity	
Anode	Anode slurry mixing	Electricity	
	Anode coating	Electricity	
	Anode electrode drying	Gas	
	Anode calendaring	Electricity	
	Anode notching	Electricity	
Cell assembly	Cell lamination	Electricity	
	Cell assembly	Electricity	
	Cell post drying	Electricity	
	Cell electrolyte filling	Electricity	
	Cell ageing & formation	Electricity	

Table 27 Energy consumption per step for GIGAGERMA
No sufficient detail was provided to understand if the room energy consumption was included, nor was the room energy consumption provided aside from it.

11.4.3. Material input, scrap rate, re-use and waste

Moreover, for each step, the exogenous material inputs were provided clearly or vaguely, and some inferences were made:

	Step	Material	Amount	Units	Assumption
Cathode	Slurry mixing	CAM		kg	
	Slurry mixing	Binder		kg	
	Slurry mixing	Binder		kg	
	Slurry mixing	Conductive Additive		kg	
	Slurry mixing	Conductive Additive		kg	
	Coating	Aluminium Foil		m ²	
Anode	Slurry mixing	AM		kg	
	Slurry mixing	Binder		kg	
	Slurry mixing	Binder		kg	
	Slurry mixing	Conductive Additive		kg	
	Slurry mixing	Conductive Additive		kg	
	Coating	Copper Foil		m ²	
Cell assembly	Lamination	Separator		m ²	
	Assembly	Pouch Foil		kg	
	Assembly	Tab		kg	
	Electrolyte filling	Electrolyte		kg	

Table 28 Material input for DE-89 GIGAGERMA cell

The following graph represents the process and induced losses. Whereas some losses can be identified to evaporation (e.g. 0.5kg during the drying process or 100% of the di-water), the losses during notching (37.5% or 0.3kg) are rather unclear. In the case of nothing, the unclear losses are modelled such as for each kg of the intermediate product received from the Calendaring step 37.5% is not provided as a “notched” electrode hence losing all the accumulated value from the previous steps.

Figure 40 GIGAGERMA production process of the DE-89 cell

11.4.4. Economic assessment

Material costs were taken from Pomega economic assessment or literature:

Material UID	Price	Price unit
NMC622	17,70 ⁶	€/kg
SP(Conductive carbon black)	7,3	€/kg
CNT(Carbon nanotubes)	4,7	€/kg
De-ionized water	0,0007	€/kg
Aluminum foil	8,4	€/kg
SBR	6,4	€/kg
Gr (graphite)	5,3	€/kg
CMC	8,2	€/kg
Copper foil	11,5	€/kg
Separator	38,1 ⁷	€/kg
Electrolyte	5,1	€/kg
Housing	0,2835 [1] ⁸	€/pc
Tab	10,322 ⁹	€/kg

Table 29 Material cost for the manufacturing of GIGAGERMA cell DE-89

For the CAM cost, we reused the value from (Greenwood, Wentker and Leker, 2021), a few costs have been translated to euros.

For de-ionized water (Water Innovations, Inc., no date) was used, this simple proxy was used due to the low impact on the total cost of de-ionized water (i.e. It is used in the same quantity as CMC but up to a few orders of magnitude cheaper). The price when compared to the one of Ecoinvent 3.10 updated to 2020 shows a difference of less than 5%.

The German energy cost (i.e. electricity and gas here) was taken from (Eurostat, 2024a) and (Eurostat, 2024b) respectively.

For electricity price, we filtered based on the last 10 years (Second semester 2013 to 2023) and for German electricity consumers of 20 MWh and above resulting in an average price of 0.1432€ kWh⁻¹.

For gas price, we selected the values for the first and second semesters of 2023 and for German electricity consumers of 20 MWh and above resulting in an average price of 0.2468€ kWh⁻¹.

No information provided by GIGAGERMA allowed us to determine the cost of labour however labour value was still collected using the same source as Pomega.

⁶ Originally 21.46\$ USD from (Greenwood, Wentker and Leker, 2021), Change rate USD to EUR from 15/06/2021

⁷ Conversion to €/kg was done using 0,4€/m² and considering 10.5g/m² (range provided is 8.5-12.5g/m²)

⁸ Cost from (Nelson *et al.*, 2019), (0.05*2.47) +0.16(US 3\$ per kg+ US 0.20\$ cell⁻¹), change rate USD to EUR from 15/06/2021

⁹ 0.62*11.5+0.38*8.4 as we reuse of Al & Cu Foil cost based on the weight share of the current collector, Change rate USD to EUR from 15/06/2021

The labour cost, 47.7€ h⁻¹, was taken from (Eurostat, 2024c) and filtered for the value corresponding to “Labour cost for LCI (compensation of employees plus taxes minus subsidies)”, for the year 2023 and averaged for a subset of the following NACE-2 sectors:

- Professional, scientific and technical activities
- Manufacturing
- Industry (except construction)

These three sectors were taken because of the highly automated and skilled industry that is the battery industry.

This labour cost is comparable to the value of 49.56\$ h⁻¹ for manufacturing provided by (Federal Statistical Office of Germany, 2021).

11.4.5. Environmental assessment

Common name	LCI	ID or name	Source	Comment
Electricity mix		market for electricity, high voltage, DE	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
NMC622	NMC622(Lithium iron phosphate)		Internal – Based on (Q. Dai et al., 2017)	
Carbon nanotube	CNT(Carbon nanotubes)	MWCNT	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122465 .	Multiwalled (MWCNT)
Graphite	Gr (graphite)		https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2022.130474	Natural
Conductive carbon black	SP(Conductive carbon black)	market for carbon black, RoW	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
CMC	CMC	carboxymethyl cellulose production, powder, RER	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
SBR	SBR		Internal VUB	
Deionised-water	Di-W	water production, deionised, RoW	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
Aluminium-foil	Aluminum foil 14um	aluminium collector foil production, for Li-ion battery	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
Copper-foil	Copper foil 8 um	copper collector foil production, for Li-ion battery	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	
Separator	separator ceramic coated PE		Research project; internal HIFI element	
Housing	Cell container multilayer pouch production		Research project; internal FIVEVB	
Electrolyte	LiPF6, EC, DMC	electrolyte production, for Li-ion battery, GLO	Ecoinvent 3.9.1	

Table 30 Background data for GIGAGERMA E-LCA

11.4.6. Social assessment

Inventory operational Inputs

Table 31. Manufacturing steps, material inputs, and countries of origin of GIGAGERMA's DE-89 Energy Cell production process. Material type: EX=Exogenous product; IN=Intermediate product; S=Scrap. The text marked in blue colour corresponds to secondary data obtained from WP6.

Step ID	Material UID	Material type	Country
Cathode manufacturing-Slurry mixing	Cathode Active Material Li(Ni0.6 Mn0.2 Co0.2)O2	EX	China, Japan, South Korea
	Cathode Binder 1	EX	Europe (Belgium, Germany, France)
	Cathode Binder 2	EX	Europe (Belgium, Germany, France)
	Cathode Conductive Additive 1	EX	China, Japan, South Korea
	Cathode Conductive Additive 2	EX	China, Japan, South Korea
Anode manufacturing-Slurry mixing	Anode Active Material Graphite	EX	China, Japan, South Korea
	Anode Binder 1	EX	China, Japan, South Korea
	Anode Binder 2	EX	China, Japan, South Korea
	Anode Conductive Additive 1	EX	Europe (Belgium, Germany, France)
	Anode Conductive Additive 2	EX	Europe (Belgium, Germany, France)
Cathode manufacturing-Coating	Aluminium Foil	EX	China, Japan, South Korea
	Cathode slurry	IN	Germany
Anode manufacturing-Coating	Copper Foil	EX	China, Japan, South Korea
	Anode slurry	IN	Germany
Cathode manufacturing-Electrode Drying	Cathode coated	IN, S	Germany
Anode manufacturing-Electrode Drying	Anode coated	IN, S	Germany
Cathode manufacturing-Calendarling	Cathode dried	IN, S	Germany
Anode manufacturing-Calendarling	Anode dried	IN, S	Germany
Cathode manufacturing-Notching	Cathode calendared	IN, S	Germany
	Anode calendared	IN, S	Germany
Cell manufacturing-Lamination	Cathode notched	IN, S	Germany
	Anode notched	IN, S	Germany
	Separator	EX	Japan, South Korea, Germany
Cell manufacturing-Assembly	Electrodes laminated	S	Germany
	Pouch Foil	EX	China, Japan, South Korea
	Tab	EX	China, Japan, South Korea
Cell manufacturing-Drying	Cell assembled	IN, S	Germany
Cell manufacturing-Electrolyte filling	Cell dried	IN, S	Germany
	Electrolyte	EX	Asia (China, Japan, South Korea)
Cell finishing-Ageing & Formation	Cell with electrolyte filled	IN, S	Germany

Table 32. Manufacturing steps, energy/water input amounts, and countries of origin of GIGAGERMA's DE-89 Energy Cell production process.

Step ID	Input	Amount	Units	Country
Anode manufacturing-Slurry mixing	Electricity		kWh	Germany

Anode manufacturing-Slurry mixing	Water as input to product		kg	Germany
Cathode manufacturing-Slurry mixing	Electricity		kWh	Germany
Cathode manufacturing-Slurry mixing	Water as input to product		kg	Germany
Anode manufacturing-Coating	Electricity		kWh	Germany
Cathode manufacturing-Coating	Electricity		kWh	Germany
Anode manufacturing-Electrode Drying	Natural gas		kWh	Germany
Cathode manufacturing-Electrode Drying	Natural gas		kWh	Germany
Cell manufacturing-Drying	Electricity		kWh	Germany
Cell finishing-Ageing & Formation	Electricity		kWh	Germany

Sector/country pair selection for costs allocation

The allocation of production cost breakdown to the corresponding social LCI dataset for every CSS was conducted based on:

- Information reported in the literature (Huisman *et al.*, 2020; Fichtner *et al.*, 2022; Das, Manna and Puravankara, 2023; Shi *et al.*, 2023) on the most common compositions of the material operational inputs specified in Table 31.
- The Detailed Sectoral List provided by GTAP (Aguilar *et al.*, 2022).

The sectors selected were:

- Metal products (fmp): Metal products production
- Metals nec (nfm): Non-ferrous metal production and casting (copper, aluminium, zinc, lead, gold, and silver)
- Chemical, rubber, plastic products (crp): Chemical, rubber and plastic product production
- Petroleum, coal products (p_c): Petroleum and coal products production
- Manufactures nec (omf): Other manufacturing
- Electricity (ely): Electricity production
- Gas manufacture, distribution (gdt): Gas distribution

An additional simplification step was done to model the system using the SHDB in SimaPro:

- For inputs coming from China, Japan or South Korea, only China and Japan (main suppliers) were considered.
- For inputs with other various origins (cathode binders, anode additives and separator), only Germany was considered.

Therefore, two case studies were proposed:

- CASE 1: China (identified as “CHN” in SHDB modelling)
- CASE 2: Japan (“JPN” in SHDB modelling)

To select the origins, an alternative approach with just one case study with market mix composed of different potential origin countries was also considered, according to the data provided by (Huisman *et al.*, 2020)] (see Figure 34). Finally, it was disregarded due to lack of data (e.g. China, Japan and South Korea supply 48%, 29% and 9% of CAM and AAM, respectively, but the rest of countries in the mix was not detailed in their report).

Results

Overall social impacts on stakeholder categories

The results obtained are shown in Table 33 and Table 34 (greatest impacts highlighted in grey), and represented for each social category in Figure 43, Figure 44, and Figure 45.

To compare the impact values in the charts of Figure 44 and Figure 45, it must be noted that the values for CASE 1-China are one order of magnitude higher than those for CASE 2-Japan.

Table 33. Social impacts on stakeholder categories in CASE 1-China and CASE 2-Japan expressed in Mrheq.

Impact category	Case 1 (Mrheq)	Case 2 (Mrheq)
1 Labor Rights & Decent Work	58,51	24,48
2 Health & Safety	98,32	40,11
3 Society	41,72	15,22
4 Governance	81,63	28,77
5 Community	38,32	16,30

Table 34. Social impacts on stakeholder categories in CASE 1-China and CASE 2-Japan expressed in Pt (after the weighting step in SimaPro).

Impact category	Case 1 (Pt)	Case 2 (Pt)
1 Labor Rights & Decent Work	8,26E+14	3,46E+14
2 Health & Safety	2,42E+17	9,87E+16
3 Society	3,75E+16	1,37E+16
4 Governance	1,08E+17	3,81E+16
5 Community	4,19E+16	1,78E+16
Total	4,30E+17	1,69E+17

Method: Social Hotspot 2021 Category Method w Weights / Equalcategoryweights / Single score / Excluding long-term emissions

Comparing 81,2 USD 2011 'DE-89Energy Cell_FU:1kWh of storage capacity_CASE 1- China' with 81,2 USD 2011 'DE-89Energy Cell_FU:1kWh of storage capacity_CASE 2 - Japan'

Figure 41. CASE 1-China vs. CASE 2-Japan: Social impacts on stakeholder categories expressed in Pt.

Figure 42. Social impacts on stakeholder categories in CASE 1-China expressed in Pt.

Method: Social Hotspot 2021 Category Method w Weights / Equalcategoryweights / Weighting / Excluding long-term emissions
 Analyzing 81,2 USD 2011 'DE-89Energy Cell_FU:1kWh of storage capacity_CASE 2 - Japan';

Figure 43. Social impacts on stakeholder categories in CASE 2-Japan expressed in Pt.

Social impacts on stakeholder categories per manufacturing step

The results are presented in Table 35 for each manufacturing step of the cells (greatest impacts highlighted in grey), and represented in Figure 46 and Figure 47. The detailed values for the operational inputs with the highest impacts are provided in Table 36, Table 37, Figure 48 and Figure 49.

Table 35. Social impacts on stakeholder categories per manufacturing process in CASE 1-China and CASE 2-Japan expressed in Pt.

Process	Case 1 (Pt)	Case 2 (Pt)
1. Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing (CHN)	1,54E+17	2,28E+16
2. Slurry mixing anode manufacturing (CHN)	9,20E+16	1,84E+16
3. Coating cathode manufacturing (CHN)	1,39E+16	8,26E+15
4. Coating anode manufacturing (CHN)	2,79E+16	1,24E+16
5. Electrode drying (DEU)	1,19E+16	1,19E+16
6. Calendaring and Notching (DEU)	2,30E+16	2,30E+16
7. Cell Lamination (DEU)	3,81E+16	3,81E+16
8. Cell Assembly (CHN)	1,40E+16	8,18E+15

Process	Case 1 (Pt)	Case 2 (Pt)
9. Cell Drying (DEU)	6,16E+15	6,16E+15
10. Electrolyte filling (CHN)	4,19E+16	1,26E+16
11. Cell finishing (Ageing&Formation) (DEU)	6,84E+15	6,84E+15
Total	4,30E+17	1,69E+17

Method: Social Hotspot 2021 Category Method w Weights / Equal category weights / Single score / Excluding long-term emissions
 Analyzing 81,2 USD 2011 DE-89Energy Cell_FU:1kWh of storage capacity_CASE 1-China;

Figure 44. Social impacts on stakeholder categories per manufacturing process in CASE 1-China expressed in Pt.

Figure 45. Social impacts on stakeholder categories per manufacturing process in CASE 2-Japan expressed in Pt.

Table 36. Greatest contributions from operational inputs to social impacts on stakeholder categories, found in process 1 (Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing) in CASE 1-China.

Process	Case 1 (Pt)
1.1 CAM	1,49E+17
1.2 Binders	2,61E+15
1.3 Conductive additives	2,87E+15
Electricity	1,10E+13
Total	1,54E+17

Figure 46. Greatest contributions from operational inputs to social impacts on stakeholder categories, found in process 1 (Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing) in CASE 1-China expressed in Pt.

Table 37. Greatest contributions from operational inputs to social impacts on stakeholder categories, found in process 7 (Cell lamination) in CASE 2-Japan.

Process	Case 2 (Pt)
7.1 Cathode and Anode notched	1,15E+16
7.2 Separator	2,66E+16
Total	3,81E+16

Figure 47. Greatest contributions from operational inputs to social impacts on stakeholder categories, found in process 7 (Cell lamination) in CASE 2-Japan expressed in Pt.

Overall social impacts on stakeholder subcategories

The results obtained are shown in Table 38 and Table 39 (with text highlighted in grey corresponding to the highest impacts), and represented for each social category in Figure 50, Figure 51, and Figure 52.

Table 38. Social impacts on stakeholder subcategories in CASE 1-China and CASE 2-Japan expressed in Mrheq.

Impact subcategory	Case 1 (Mrheq)	Case 2 (Mrheq)
1.A Wage Assessments	12,34	6,35
1.C Workers in poverty	8,32	3,73
1.D Child Labor	7,32	3,69
1.E Forced Labor	12,63	5,76
1.F Excessive Working Time	13,76	5,55
1.G Freedom of Association	15,58	4,26
1.H Migrant Labor	6,82	3,14
1.I Social Benefits	7,52	2,11
1.J Labor Laws/Conventions	2,34	1,45
1.K Discrimination and equal opportunity	13,07	5,41
1.L Unemployment	7,56	3,43
2.A Occupational Toxics & Hazards	18,71	5,46
2.B Injuries and Fatalities	14,06	7,91
3.A Indigenous Rights	5,44	1,86
3.B Gender Equity	5,38	2,41
3.C High Conflict Zones	10,75	3,66

Impact subcategory	Case 1 (Mrheq)	Case 2 (Mrheq)
3.D Human Health Issues - NCDs and other	1,28	0,64
3.E Human Health Issues - Commun. Dis.	0,00	0,00
3.F Poverty & inequality	12,49	4,37
3.G State of environmental sust.	13,33	4,81
4.A Legal System	13,99	5,12
4.B Corruption	5,16	2,09
4.C Democracy & freedom of speech	21,66	7,17
5.A Access to Improved Drinking Water	4,42	2,22
5.B Access to Improved Sanitation	7,10	3,61
5.C Children out of School	10,71	3,37
5.D Health Care System Access	6,15	3,39
5.E Smallholder v. Commercial Farms	7,52	1,56
5.F Access to electricity	2,05	1,11
5.G Property rights	6,74	3,76

Table 39. Social impacts on stakeholder subcategories in CASE 1-China and CASE 2-Japan expressed in Pt (after the weighting step in SimaPro).

Impact subcategory	Case 1 (Pt)	Case 2 (Pt)
1.A Wage Assessments	9,89E+15	5,09E+15
1.C Workers in poverty	8,12E+15	3,64E+15
1.D Child Labor	5,51E+15	2,78E+15
1.E Forced Labor	1,78E+16	8,12E+15
1.F Excessive Working Time	1,32E+16	5,31E+15
1.G Freedom of Association	1,08E+16	2,96E+15
1.H Migrant Labor	3,26E+15	1,50E+15
1.I Social Benefits	2,24E+15	6,27E+14
1.J Labor Laws/Conventions	4,12E+14	2,56E+14
1.K Discrimination and equal opportunity	1,70E+16	7,02E+15
1.L Unemployment	5,95E+15	2,70E+15
2.A Occupational Toxics & Hazards	2,57E+16	7,50E+15
2.B Injuries and Fatalities	1,91E+16	1,08E+16
3.A Indigenous Rights	2,07E+15	7,10E+14
3.B Gender Equity	2,78E+15	1,25E+15
3.C High Conflict Zones	5,31E+15	1,81E+15
3.D Human Health Issues - NCDs and other	2,12E+14	1,06E+14
3.E Human Health Issues - Commun. Dis.	0	0
3.F Poverty & inequality	5,78E+15	2,02E+15
3.G State of environmental sust.	1,21E+16	4,35E+15
4.A Legal System	1,25E+16	4,59E+15
4.B Corruption	2,99E+15	1,21E+15
4.C Democracy & freedom of speech	1,59E+16	5,26E+15

Impact subcategory	Case 1 (Pt)	Case 2 (Pt)
5.A Access to Improved Drinking Water	2,71E+15	1,36E+15
5.B Access to Improved Sanitation	4,82E+15	2,45E+15
5.C Children out of School	6,48E+15	2,04E+15
5.D Health Care System Access	6,85E+15	3,78E+15
5.E Smallholder v. Commercial Farms	9,07E+14	1,88E+14
5.F Access to electricity	3,75E+14	2,02E+14
5.G Property rights	6,31E+15	3,52E+15
Total	2,27E+17	9,31E+16

It can be observed that the total impacts on the stakeholder subcategories expressed in points are different from those calculated using the SHI 1 Category method. This is because the number of subcategories within each category and the number of indicators within each subcategory are not the same, and SHI 1 and SHI2 methods are different in terms of the characterisation and weighting factors applied.

Figure 48. CASE 1-China vs. CASE 2-Japan: Social impacts on stakeholder subcategories expressed in Pt.

Method: Social Hotspot 2021 Subcategory Method w Weights / Equalsubcatweights / Weighting / Excluding long-term emissions
 Analyzing 81,2 USD 2011 'DE-89Energy Cell_FU:1kWh of storage capacity_CASE 1- China';

Figure 49. Social impacts on stakeholder subcategories in CASE 1-China expressed in Pt.

Figure 50. Social impacts on stakeholder subcategories in CASE 2-Japan expressed in Pt.

Social impacts on stakeholder subcategories per manufacturing step

The results are presented in Table 40 for each manufacturing step of the cells (with text highlighted in grey corresponding to the highest impacts), and represented in Figure 53 and Figure 54. The detailed values for the operational inputs with the highest impacts are provided in Table 41, Table 42, Figure 55 and Figure 56.

Table 40. Social impacts on stakeholder subcategories per manufacturing process in CASE 1- China and CASE 2-Japan expressed in Pt.

Process	Case 1 (Pt)	Case 2 (Pt)
1. Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing	8,00E+16	1,27E+16
2. Slurry mixing anode manufacturing	4,86E+16	1,05E+16
3. Coating cathode manufacturing	7,42E+15	4,53E+15
4. Coating anode manufacturing	1,48E+16	6,87E+15
5. Electrode drying	6,44E+15	6,44E+15
6. Calendaring and Notching	1,25E+16	1,25E+16
7. Cell Lamination	2,11E+16	2,11E+16
8. Cell Assembly	7,43E+15	4,49E+15
9. Cell Drying	3,33E+15	3,33E+15
10. Electrolyte filling	2,18E+16	7,00E+15
11. Cell finishing (Ageing&Formation)	3,69E+15	3,69E+15
Total	2,27E+17	9,31E+16

Figure 51. Social impacts on stakeholder subcategories per manufacturing process in CASE 1-China expressed in Pt.

Figure 52. Social impacts on stakeholder subcategories per manufacturing process in CASE 2-Japan expressed in Pt.

Table 41. Greatest contributions from operational inputs to social impacts on stakeholder subcategories, found in process 1 (Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing) in CASE 1-China.

Process	Case 1 (Pt)
1.1 CAM	7,71E+16
1.2 Binders	1,46E+15
1.3 Conductive additives	1,48E+15
Electricity	5,81E+12
Total	8,00E+16

Figure 53. Greatest contributions from operational inputs to social impacts on stakeholder subcategories, found in process 1 (Slurry mixing cathode manufacturing) in CASE 1-China expressed in Pt.

Table 42. Greatest contributions from operational inputs to social impacts on stakeholder subcategories, found in process 7 (Cell lamination) in CASE 2-Japan.

Process	Case 2 (Pt)
7.1 Cathode and Anode notched	6,23E+15
7.2 Separator	1,49E+16
Total	2,11E+16

Figure 54. Greatest contributions from operational inputs to social impacts on stakeholder subcategories, found in process 7 (Cell lamination) in CASE 2-Japan expressed in Pt.